

BEUCITIZEN
BARRIERS TOWARDS EU CITIZENSHIP

Final Report on dissemination activities

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. COMMUNICATION TOOLS	5
2.1 Public Website	5
2.1.1. Structure of the website	6
2.1.2 Website visibility	7
2.2. Social networks	7
2.3 Newsletter	9
2.3.1 Structure	9
2.3.2 Preparation and distribution	9
2.4 POLICY BRIEFS	10
2.4.1 Structure	10
2.3.3 Frequency and distribution	10
3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	12
3.1 Conferences and Workshops	12
3.1.1 annual conferences	12
3.1.2 Workshops & other events.....	14
3.2 Participation to external events.....	17
3.3 Publication of projects results: “Interdisciplinary Perspectives on EU Citizenship” book series	17
4. EU CITIZENSHIP TEACHING PACKAGES FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL PUPIL	18
5. OTHER DISSEMINATION TOOLS	19
Videos 20	
Circus Europe	20
6. CONCLUSIONS	21
ANNEXES – TABLE DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	22

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of Deliverable 12.5 - Final Report on Dissemination structure is to report all dissemination activities and communication tools which have been developed, implemented and applied during the project lifetime. In particular, bEUcitizen dissemination instruments and activities include:

- a dedicated project website (www.beucitizen.eu) allowing for fast and easy communication of the most relevant information and news to a wide audience;
- a newsletter, which has been issued biannually during the project to inform relevant stakeholders about the key achievements and the next activities planned;
- a number of 7 Policy Briefs have been released during the project with the aim to spread policy scenarios and recommendations;
- a series of five teaching packages for secondary school pupils in the age group of 14-16/17, which will be distributed via the project website;
- public workshops and events have also been organized with the main purpose of getting potential stakeholders directly involved in the work, but also for gathering feedback about the activities performed by the Consortium;
- representatives of the bEUcitizen Consortium have also attended external public events presenting the activities performed and the results achieved by the project.

Furthermore, the most relevant outcomes, which will be presented during the Final Conference, to be held in Brussels on 26-28 April 2017, have been collected in a book series that will be published in September 2017 by Edward Elgar Publishing.

1. INTRODUCTION

The bEUcitizen project sets out to identify, investigate, discuss and propose ways to break down the barriers to the active use of EU citizenship rights – and to improve citizens’ knowledge of them and the duties they confer.

Not only does our project provide a comparative overview and classification of the various barriers to the exercise of the rights and obligations of EU citizens in the Member States and some candidate countries; it also analyses whether and how such barriers can be overcome, and looks at which strategies and narratives can be developed to strengthen EU citizenship. The insights in our findings were developed by studying citizenship from the point of view of different disciplines: law, political science, social sciences, history, philosophy, public administration and economics.

The challenges that the EU and its citizens are facing (widening inequality; the rise of populism and Euro-skepticism; challenges to open borders and mobility; the consequences of the Brexit referendum; etc.) do not only demand an improved narrative on European citizenship but also new visions of European citizenship of the future. For the last 4 years bEUcitizen has been exploring these challenges and during the final dissemination conference in Brussels (April 2017) it can reveal how best to respond to them.

This document strongly builds on deliverable 12.1 *Dissemination plan* and deliverable 12.4 *Dissemination strategy* and aims to provide an overview of the type of activities that have been carried out and how they contributed to the overall intended impacts of the project. The following intended impacts were identified in the original project proposal for the bEUcitizen project: 1) *A boost in academic research on EU citizenship*, 2) *Policy development, implementation and evaluation to encourage citizenship and remove barriers*, and 3) *Civil realisation of EU citizenship rights and responsibilities*.

In deliverable 12.4 we identified three target groups, corresponding to the three points of intended impact: 1) *Academic community*, 2) *Policy makers* and 3) *Young Europeans under the age of 35*.

In light of the aforementioned impact and target groups, this final report provides an overview of the communication tools that have been developed and implemented to maximize the visibility of the project (Chapter 2) and of the dissemination activities organized and events attended by bEUcitizen consortium partners and individual researchers (Chapter 3). Chapter 4 describes the teaching material that will be published on the project website. Finally, Chapter 5 will take into consideration the other visual dissemination and communication tools we adopted.

2. COMMUNICATION TOOLS

A broad array of dissemination channels have been conceived and implemented to boost the visibility of the project and in order to guarantee that the most relevant project outcomes were communicated to the widest audience possible, in the most effective way.

2.1 PUBLIC WEBSITE

The Internet represents at present one of the main communication media, allowing the dissemination of any kind of information to a wide audience in a fast and accessible manner. The website represents an immediate and easy-to-access entry point which is open to all relevant stakeholders, and thus able to create awareness and interest about the project by making the most important information publicly available in a concise but exhaustive manner.

The bEUcitizen public website was created at the beginning of the project and made available at <http://www.beucitizen.eu/>.

2.1.1. STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE

The website contains four pages that have constantly been updated (other pages are more static in nature and did not need to be updated regularly, as “Our project” and “Our people”):

1. *News*: where documents published by the European Institutions, news or other information of interest both for our researchers and for the public interested in the topic have been made available. It has been applied as reference to any kind of news which has been considered relevant in the scope of the project;
2. *Blog*: updated with contributions written by researchers;
3. *Agenda*: with upcoming events organized within the Consortium or by third-parties;
4. *Publications*: where all the project deliverables and other publications have been uploaded or announced.

FIGURE 1 -SCREENSHOT OF THE WEBSITE HOMEPAGE

Visitors were given the possibility to leave comments through a moderated communication interface.

2.1.2 WEBSITE VISIBILITY

The effectiveness of the project website as a dissemination tool strongly depends on its visibility through the main internet search engines. Therefore, the public website has been properly designed and structured in order to ensure that it is displayed within the very first results as selected by search engines.

In order to achieve this goal, relevant terms have been embedded as meta-keywords in the programming language used to structure the website, so that they are visible and recognizable by the internet searching tools.

2.2. SOCIAL NETWORKS

BEUcitizen made also use of social networks, as Twitter and Facebook. These more recent communication channels enable to reach and to interact with the widest audience possible and to keep a fast-moving flow of project news.

The distribution of messages and their reception through the virtual community are shown by the number of likes, sharing and comments on Facebook or by the number of followers, citations and Retweets on Twitter.

FIGURE 2 - FACEBOOK PAGE

FIGURE 3 - TWITTER ACCOUNT

As most organizations and professionals are active on Twitter, it served as an important dissemination platform through which reports and outcomes were circulated. Updates prior to and during events were spread via Twitter (for example, during the 2014 annual meeting, a hashtag (#) was used), as it enabled all stakeholders to the project to easily be updated on what is happening in the project itself.

Furthermore, Twitter was used to gather and forward interesting news on the topic of EU Citizenship. In particular, bEUcitizen was connected to the pre-existing dissemination channel of the European Commission and other European Institutions.

In addition, an insights tool developed by Facebook allowed us to monitor the post reach and the number of viewers.

FIGURE 4 - FACEBOOK INSIGHTS

2.3 NEWSLETTER

The main purpose of the newsletter was to provide up-to-date information to interested parties about the activities performed within the scope of the project, results achieved as well as upcoming events of interests.

2.3.1 STRUCTURE

The structure of the newsletter has been modified through different issues, depending on the necessity of the information to be reported in a particular issue. However, in general, the document has been structured on the basis of the following sections:

- Editorial: written by the project Coordinator, it provides a general overview of the status of the project, and an introduction to the content of the other sections;
- Latest research findings and progress: different sections dedicated to the detailed description of activities and results achieved; written by the partner responsible for the work done (i.e. the relevant WP Leader or Task Leader). The number of such sections have been dynamic in the various issues of the newsletter, depending on the topics to be reported;
- Report on past events organized by Consortium Partners;
- Agenda: section focused on presenting the main events as scheduled in the near future. This included those organized within the scope of the project, as well as external events of particular relevance.

2.3.2 PREPARATION AND DISTRIBUTION

Bi-annually an email newsletter was sent out, in June and December. The months were chosen to best fit the annual agenda of the project. By bringing out a newsletter in June, the latest news from the annual consortium meeting could be included. In December, the newsletter functioned as a closing for the year, summarizing the progress made and looking forward to the next calendar year just before the Christmas break.

A professional newsletter design has been developed in order to provide for a recognizable identity to the project. The content of the newsletter was elaborated by the coordination team, in cooperation with the Work package coordinators.

Newsletters were prepared and distributed with the support of Campaign Builder, which allows the printing of high-quality paper copies, and the conversion of the file in PDF format for the dissemination via e-mail and through the website.

Their success continuously increased, reaching and passing the number of 200 subscriptions (this numbers show that not only bEUcitizen consortium members, but also external scholars and the general public subscribed to the newsletter).

A total of 6 newsletters were published during the lifetime of the project, more precisely :

- [Newsletter 1](#), December 2013, which presented the project, the activities performed during the first six months and reported on the kick-off meeting;
- [Newsletter 2](#), July 2014, with a focus on the first research results and on the first annual meeting in Istanbul from June 30th to July 2nd 2014;
- [Newsletter 3](#), December 2014, gave visibility to the achievement of three important deliverables (D3.1, D7.1 and D9.1). Furthermore, the newsletter served as means of

distribution of the Call for papers for the 2015 Mid - Term Conference, entitled: Being a Citizen in Europe (Zagreb, 2015);

- [Newsletter 4](#), August 2015 reflected on the "Being a citizen in Europe" Conference held in Zagreb (29-30 June 2015), reported on the parallel workshop organized for students "Breaking Down Barriers: Future scenarios on youth and citizenship in 2030 – Youth and access to education, labor and political decision making" and on the Circus Europe Art Exhibition;
- [Newsletter 5](#), January 2016, which presented the latest deliverables published and the most important results achieved so far; and
- [Newsletter 6](#), February 2017, which contained an overview on the six Policy Briefs released by bEUcitizen Consortium members and presented the bEUcitizen Final Conference.

A 7th newsletter will be issued after the end of the project and will report on the bEUcitizen Final Conference "The Future of EU citizenship".

In addition, the newsletter was also used to circulate the [Call for Papers](#) for the two-day international and interdisciplinary conference "Being a Citizen in Europe", which took place on 29 - 30 June 2015 in Zagreb (Croatia).

2.4 POLICY BRIEFS

Seven policy briefs have been produced by the project to communicate policy relevant results and to attract the highest attention from policymaking and policy decision circles.

The purpose of the policy briefs is to raise awareness inside the decision makers and general public communities on themes related to the research topics of bEUcitizen. The content of the policy briefs consisted of short presentations, in the form of constructive policy recommendations, in which researchers could articulate their evidence-based conclusions.

2.4.1 STRUCTURE

The policy briefs were structured in accordance with the European Policy Brief template provided by the European Commission. In addition to the title and author, every policy brief is composed of 5 sections: introduction, key observations, policy implications and recommendations, research parameters and, to conclude, the project identity information.

The introduction helps the reader to link the title with the broad topic and the research purpose. The key observations are data on which the findings refer to. The policy implications and recommendations are the real core of the document: they are the analysis of the information available, they propose alternative evolution scenarios and suggest the best way to move forward. The section "research parameters" recalls the objective of the bEUcitizen project and its research methodology (multidisciplinary and multidimensional, combining normative and empirical disciplines). The project identity section states the general info of the project: name, coordinator, consortium members, funding scheme, duration and budget.

2.3.3 FREQUENCY AND DISTRIBUTION

Six policy briefs have been released in January 2017. At the time of writing, one policy brief is still under revision and it will be published by mid-April 2017.

All policy briefs have been published on the bEUcitizen website, under "[Publications](#)" and on the bEUcitizen Final Conference website, under About the conference > [Additional materials](#).

Furthermore, they were circulated within our mailing list with Newsletter n.6, February 2017, and they will be printed and distributed at the final conference (26-28 April 2017, Brussels).

All policy briefs can be downloaded from the aforementioned online webpages.

EUROPEAN POLITICAL CITIZENSHIP 2030: POST-DEMOCRACY WITH POPULIST ACTIVISM OR AN INTEGRATED POLITICAL AND SOCIAL CITIZENSHIP?

Policy scenarios and recommendations from bEUcitizen, a research project on the barriers to realise and exercise citizenship rights by European Union citizens

Written by
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December 2016

INTRODUCTION

This is a brief in the bEUcitizen policy brief series. The bEUcitizen project - funded by the European Union - set out to identify, investigate, discuss, and ameliorate the barriers to the active use of rights (and knowledge of duties, the concomitant to rights, in so far as there are any) by European citizens. The project aimed to provide a comparative overview and classification of the various barriers to the exercise of the rights and obligations of European Union citizens in the member states. Simultaneously, the project analysed whether and how such barriers can be overcome and the future opportunities and challenges the European Union and its member states face to further develop the idea and reality of European Union citizenship.

Drawing on research conducted during the project, this policy brief discusses the problems preventing European Union citizens from becoming active political citizens. European citizenship as active political citizenship has been underdeveloped from the start and is currently under strong pressure. Over time, European Union citizens seem to have lost enthusiasm for the European political process: Voter turnout in European Parliament elections decreased from 61,99% in 1979 to 42,61% in 2014. Attempts to transform elections for the European Parliament into a meaningful decision about the policies and the personnel of European institutions have been ineffective so far in two ways: On the one hand, they did not raise more interest in European affairs; on the other hand, and even more problematically, the 'Spitzenkandidaten'-experiment was overshadowed by the power struggle between national leaders and the European Parliament.

Although similar tendencies towards decreasing voter turnout can be observed in national elections, the trend of fading popular support is particularly alarming

FIGURE 5 - COVER PAGE POLICY BRIEF

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1 CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS

The most important channel for engaging with the Academic Community and Policy Makers was to organize, attend and present at high-level conferences and events.

If during the first years the main aim of these presentations was to introduce bEUcitizen to the Academic Community, in the last year, when results were available, conferences and seminars became the main ground to discuss findings, to collect suggestions and to exchange knowledge with other scholars and professionals.

Furthermore, conferences and national events proved to be important opportunities for involving local policy makers and civil society organizations.

Setting up an efficient structure for the dissemination activities that involve all consortium partners was one of the main goals. Part of this structure is that all partners in the consortium organized local dissemination events in their home countries, and, when possible, in their own language.

During the lifetime of the project four Annual Conferences and many seminars and workshops have been organized. Here below we list the most relevant ones.

3.1.1 ANNUAL CONFERENCES

Kick-off 2013 (Utrecht, The Netherlands)

The bEUcitizen kick-off event took place in Utrecht, 18-20 September 2013. Researchers from many different disciplines, representing 26 partner universities from the European Union and outside, met during the three day event.

The first day was an introductory day, giving people the chance to meet each other. The day ended with a round table discussion, the 'Open Forum', which was open for the general public. During this even important questions regarding European citizenship were raised and the Open Forum served as inspiration and input for the days ahead. Furthermore, representatives of the European Commission presented the 'EU Citizenship Report 2013', which had been freshly published.

During the second and third day of the Kick-Off, the work package coordinators met with their work package participants and discussed concepts, definitions, issues and planning. Overall the discussions were lively and they showed the strong commitment of the researchers, as well as the challenges faced ahead and innovative nature of the project by merging so many scientific disciplines. The Kick-Off was concluded by a plenary session where work packages reported on the work done and a number of administrative announcements and presentations.

1st general Assembly 2014 (Istanbul, Turkey)

The first bEUcitizen Annual Conference was held in Istanbul from June 29th to July 2nd 2014. During this three day conference, researchers discussed the content of the work, challenged each other, found fields of interest on which they could work together with a view to improve the academic output and effectiveness within the project. In this context, an open Forum discussion has been organised, to which a broad audience was actively invited.

2nd General Assembly and Mid-Term Conference 2015 (Zagreb, Croatia)

From June 29th until July 2nd 2015, the Faculty of Political Science and Hotel Dubrovnik in Zagreb (Croatia) hosted the 2015 bEUcitizen Annual Conference. The second consortium meeting included also a two-day international and interdisciplinary conference on the theme: "Being a citizen in Europe" (29-30 June). During this two day conference, researchers from the bEUcitizen research project and external scholars, participating in panel discussions, which were divided into four streams, talked about different aspects of European citizenship.

On Monday June 29 a parallel workshop ("Breaking down barriers: future scenarios on youth and citizenship in 2030 – Youth and access to education, labour and political decision-making") gave the opportunity to twenty students and young professionals to discuss different future scenarios for youth-citizenship. The outcomes were presented during the Conference closing.

The second part of the Conference was dedicated to the Work Package meetings, where researchers discussed the content of their work, the progress made and looked ahead, planning the activities for the coming two years.

3rd General Assembly 2016 (Oviedo, Spain)

FIGURE 6 - MEDIA COVERAGE OVIEDO

The 2016 bEUcitizen consortium meeting took place in Oviedo (Spain) from June 29th until July 1st 2016. The main focus and purpose of the conference was to facilitate the integration of the findings in the different work packages and look ahead towards the end of the project, planning the books and the book series. In order for the consortium to really focus on their work in the bEUcitizen project, a choice was made not to invite outside keynote speakers to this last working conference for the project. Nevertheless, initiated by the PR department of the University of Oviedo, there proved to be much interest in the bEUcitizen project when we arrived in Oviedo. The first day of the conference, several (local) media were present at the conference location looking for interviews with bEUcitizen researchers. This resulted in media coverage for the project in newspapers and on television.

Final consortium meeting and final conference 2017 (Brussels, Belgium)

The final conference of the bEUcitizen project, titled “*The Future of EU citizenship*” will take place from 26 to 28 April 2016, in Brussels (at the time of writing it is being organized and a report on the event will be made available immediately after).

The final event will present and discuss the main results of the bEUcitizen project and its policy recommendations. Beside a number of participants of the bEUcitizen consortium, the following speakers will be involved in the panel debates: *Kalypso Nicolaidis* (St Antony's College - University of Oxford), *Catherine Barnard* (University of Cambridge), *Richard Bellamy* (European University Institute, Florence), *Sascha Prechal* (judge CJEU), *Stefaan van der Jeught* (CJEU and Vrije Universiteit Brussel), *Herwig Verschueren* (Antwerp), *Agnes Jongerius* (MEP), *Catherine Woollard* (ECRE) and *Eve Geddie* (PICUM).

During the conference there will be ample opportunity to engage in discussions with European institutions, academia and stakeholders. In particular, two lunch sessions tailored to policy makers and members of Parliament will be organised, which will focus on the implications of the bEUcitizen studies, their background and policy recommendations. As a kick off a future creating workshop on European Citizenship (*The future of Europe - Exploring strategies for strengthening EU Citizenship*) will be held during the first afternoon. Together with different groups of youth, members of the European Parliament, civil servants from several countries and NGO representatives, scenarios will be explored for strengthening EU citizenship in the 21st century.

This conference is open to all stakeholders interested in EU citizenship and this includes but is not limited to academics, policy makers, general public as well as representatives of all relevant organizations.

3.1.2 WORKSHOPS & OTHER EVENTS

“EU citizenship & rights” International Research Seminar 11 December 2014, Copenhagen (Denmark)

On 11 December 2014 the seminar “EU Citizenship and Rights” was organised at Copenhagen University, in a co-operation between the bEUcitizen project, University of Utrecht’s research group RENFORCE (Centre for Regulation and Enforcement of Europe) and the University of Copenhagen’s research centre CESEL (Centre for European Studies in Economic Law).

At the seminar, outstanding scholars of both universities and members of the bEUcitizen project discussed the different rights of EU citizens from various perspectives. For instance, the political dimension of EU citizenship was debated and the question was posed whether EU citizenship enhances political participation. The internal market as a driving force of EU citizenship was discussed, causing a lively debate on the constitutional nature of EU citizenship, as well as its market-origin. Furthermore, several presentations focused on the interplay of, and tension between, fundamental rights and EU citizenship, for instance in the context of criminal law and EU criminal policy. In the last session, the Dano case was extensively discussed, raising the question about the balance between EU citizenship rights and the protection of national welfare systems. Finally, the last presentations focused on the role of language, either as a barrier for EU citizens and as a tool of the Court of Justice in its reasoning.

The seminar showcased the outstanding research done in this field by the researchers affiliated to the bEUcitizen project, RENFORCE and CESEL. The presentations provided food for thought and triggered a lively debate on the rights and the nature of EU citizenship.

Seminar 'Current issues facing European citizenship' organized by bEUcitizen and the Government of Catalonia, 5 May 2015, Barcelona (Spain)

European citizenship, created by the 1992 Maastricht Treaty which came into effect that same year, placed importance for the first time on people and their rights and duties. Albeit to a limited degree, the Treaty, and later on the European Charter of Fundamental Rights, defined a core set of rights and duties that make up European citizenship. However, this citizenship, which includes, for example, the right to free movement and residence throughout the EU, may be limited by the policies of member states, which ultimately are the ones who decide the European Union's lines of political, economic and social action. Furthermore, the deficits of democratic legitimacy that blight the European institutions highlight the need to introduce new structures or to modify said institutions to bring them closer to citizens and to channel forms of participation that might increase democratic quality.

Under the title "Qüestions actuals sobre la ciutadania europea" (Current issues facing European citizenship) the Catalan Government's Institut d'Estudis Autònoms (Autonomic Studies Institute) in collaboration with bEUcitizen organized this seminar, which was attended by about 50 people, including university professors from different disciplines (including the bEUcitizen coordinator Sybe De Vries and other consortium members), senior civil servants and officials from the Government of Catalonia and undergraduate and doctorate students.

A roundtable on 'National identities and European Citizenship: A legitimacy conflict?' 7 May 2015, Barcelona (Spain)

Coordinated by Jacint Jordana, the roundtable, organized by the Institut Barcelona d'Estudis Internacionals (IBEI), brought together Francis Cheneval from the University of Zurich, Carme Colomina from the newspaper ARA and Juan Díez Medrano from the Universidad Carlos III.

Panelists discussed what we can expect from the European political citizenship, and whether barriers can prevent identity and national consolidation. To this end, the experience of Switzerland was brought to the table as an example of the challenges and expectations of an EU citizenship, which was then combined with an analysis of EU citizens' awareness of their rights and support of EU citizenship. These various dimensions were critically assessed within the current institutional and socio-political context, which is marked by existing conflicts between legitimacy and identity at the EU level, on the one hand, and the preferences and identities of member states on the other, as clearly portrayed today by the Greek crisis.

The final question and answer session enabled the public to engage in closer dialogue with the panelists.

International Conference "Making Free Movement Work" 15 June 2015, London (UK)

The aim of this event was to provide a factual overview of free movement in the context of the UK Government's stated commitment to holding a referendum on Britain's continued membership of the EU within the next two years. Presenters engaged with the theme from the perspectives of the EU regulatory framework through to those engaged with local service delivery and EU citizens' rights. The speakers, among which bEUcitizen researchers Martin Seeleib-Kaiser and Frans Pennings, prompted a wide-ranging discussion with members of the audience, who brought their own academic, frontline and policymaking perspectives to the conversation.

The report of the event can be downloaded [here](#).

Breaking Down Barriers: Future scenarios on youth and citizenship in 2030 – Youth Side Event at the bEUcitizen 2015 Mid-Term Conference 29/30 June 2015, Zagreb

On the 29th of June, a group of 20 students and young professionals from Croatia, Slovenia and the Netherlands discussed different future scenarios for youth-citizenship. They analyzed and discussed the present situation and determined what they regard as important for youth. In addition, they looked at what different ways the European societies, and especially Croatia, might develop and which consequences these would involve. How could the world look in 2030?

It took five steps to answer this question. First of all, the youth-participants determined six important values for youth citizenship after which they came up with four driving forces in society. Based on these forces, four future-world scenarios were imagined. These extreme, but possible situations were given a name and were assessed based on the aforementioned values. Last but not least, the participants had to think of a possible repertoire of action to make sure that, even in these extreme worlds, the important values be achievable for youth.

FIGURE 7 - YOUTH EVENT

The outcomes were presented during the Conference closing.

The report of the event can be downloaded [here](#)

Workshop “Barriers’ to the exercise of EU citizenship’s rights. Factual and legal analysis” 12 May 2016, Trento (Italy)

On Thursday 12 May 2016 the University of Trento (Faculty of Law), in collaboration with Utrecht University, organized the workshop “Barriers’ to the exercise of EU citizenship’s rights. Legal and factual analysis”. The research carried out in the bEUcitizen project shown a variety of barriers to EU citizenship in different fields of the law. The Trento seminar therefore aimed at stimulating an interdisciplinary and comparative dialogue among experts – especially young scholars – and participants’ critical thinking skills and ideas on the bEUcitizen key concept of “barrier” and on different kinds of hindrances, with the purpose of a scientific and critical categorization of them.

To properly deal with all these issues, the seminar was divided into three sessions: a number of lectures given by invited key note speakers – among them, the project coordinator prof. Sybe de Vries; and two round tables focusing on two opposite, but to some extent interrelated, perspectives: “from legal towards factual barriers” and “from factual towards legal barriers”.

Workshop “Beyond Renationalization and Parlamentarization. What ways to overcome the EU’s crisis of democratic representation” 23-24 June 2016, Frankfurt (Germany)

Organized by members of the bEUcitizen project at Goethe University Frankfurt this international workshop discussed the future of democratic representation in the EU. It brought together international scholars from political theory with EU scholars. The workshop participants set out to put established views of both the concept of democratic representation and the nature of the EU-polity on trial to explore possible ways out of the EU’s crisis of democratic representation. They addressed the problems of the current institutional set up of the EU under the heading of the two alternatives: returning to the intergovernmental mode of cooperation between nation states (renationalization) or a full-fledged federalization of the EU (parliamentarization). With both ways having their specific

problems, the question remains how a viable system of democratic representation in the EU beyond renationalization and parliamentarization could look like.

Workshop “Urban governance and the future of European Citizenship” (Oxford, UK)

This Workshop was organised by Maarten Prak and Josephine van Zeben and took place on 17 and 18 February 2017 at Worcester College, University of Oxford (UK).

The workshop combined a historical perspective on the role of the nation-state with a bottom-up view of the European Union, focusing on sub-state actors, in order to provide additional insights as to the future of European citizenship. The initial discussion point was that new perspectives on European citizenship and governance are urgently needed, especially now that the British referendum has highlighted the level of disenchantment of citizens with the European project. Apart from the free movement of EU citizens, the most widespread grievance refers to a ‘disconnect’ between citizens in their local and national communities and the European ‘technocrats’ in Brussels. Further centralization at the European level is likely to reinforce, rather than lessen such concerns. Over the course of this two day workshop, the aim was to draw up an inventory of the ‘state-of play’ in connection with local governance and citizenship, to exchange views, perspectives and relevant data, and to develop a shared agenda and framework for future interdisciplinary work in this area. Concretely, the resulting collection of papers from this workshop is foreseen to be published as a special issue in a top journal in citizenship or local government studies.

3.2 PARTICIPATION TO EXTERNAL EVENTS

The bEUcitizen community participated in many external events related to the topic of the projects. They were a precious opportunity to further spread the research outcomes and interact with different stakeholders.

From the very beginning, all our researchers have been asked to keep track of the activities undertaken that represented a mean to circulate our project and to create awareness about it.

Annex 1 (Table on dissemination activities) gives an overview of the main, very successful dissemination activities performed during the entire project lifecycle. These activities aimed at promoting the project, both through the direct dissemination of research results and referring to bEUcitizen during other events. Our researchers took part in different conferences, addressing a public of experts. But they also lectured to students and school children. Some researchers have published in scientific journals, referring directly to bEUcitizen.

The table is structured as follows: details of the consortium member, researcher who carried out the activity, description of the activity, further information about the activity itself; target group. Furthermore, all listed activities are accompanied by evidences, available upon request or by following the links provided.

3.3 PUBLICATION OF PROJECTS RESULTS: “INTERDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVES ON EU CITIZENSHIP” BOOK SERIES

In addition to the publication of articles in scientific journals, which guarantees an effective dissemination of specific project results, allowing to target groups of experts in the sectors addressed by bEUcitizen (see table 1, Annex), the results coming from the different Work Packages have been collected in a book series: *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on EU Citizenship*.

The series looks into the main issues relating to EU citizenship, and citizenship in general, from different angles and from a multi-disciplinary approach. It approaches and analyses the concept of EU citizenship in a coherent and integrative manner, yet from a set of unique and distinct perspectives. The point of departure is that citizenship is not merely a legal notion of rights produced by statute and/or case law, but something that has developed and develops in the interchange between rules and practices, between law, politics and society. So studying citizenship issues requires an interdisciplinary approach, which is offered by the interdisciplinary team of contributors to the series from various relevant disciplines including: law, philosophy, history, sociology, political science, economics and policy studies. This important series addresses both the normative and empirical dimensions of citizenship, and will further stir the debate on citizenship questions in Europe and beyond.

The audience for the book series is varied. The book series will appeal first of all to academics and students in quite a variety of academic disciplines. The latter are organized in relative large academic associations, in which many members of our research team actively participate, in some cases also in their leadership. Hence the book series will be promoted through their communication channels: conferences, email-networks, websites, etc.

Furthermore, given the fact that 'citizenship right issues' figure prominently on the EU-policymaking agenda, the book series addresses practitioners and policymakers in European institutions as well as in the national political, administrative and policy advisory institutions in the different EU Member States, and especially their aides, commercial policy advisors, and the numerous lawyers and lobbyist organizations in Brussels.

Finally, the books might be used in academic courses on a variety of topics and in quite a variety of academic disciplines: law, history, geography, philosophy, political science, social policy, sociology, socio-legal studies or economics.

4. EU CITIZENSHIP TEACHING PACKAGES FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL PUPIL

In this chapter we report on the teaching packages for secondary school pupils in the age group of 14-16/17, which are available on the bEUcitizen website <http://beucitizen.eu/teaching-packages/> and which will be shared on the website https://europa.eu/teachers-corner/content/homepage_en

More attention for EU Citizenship is relevant for several reasons. It first refers to the set of civil, political, economic and social rights that all citizens of EU countries possess in addition to the rights that come with their national citizenship. Secondly, it refers to the membership of a European political community in which each citizen of an EU country can participate actively; next to or intertwined with, being active in a local or national political community.

One of the conclusions from a comparative study of civic education in 7 EU-countries (D8.10 bEUcitizen), is that adolescents are hardly educated in what their EU citizenship rights are, nor are they trained in competencies to realize or enforce these rights. Parallel to this, young adults leave secondary school without being taught the civic and political competencies to participate in the variety of political communities on different levels they belong to.

EU citizenship is relevant when you stay in your country of origin and in the town you grew up in. For instance, in one's role as a consumer. Furthermore, political participation manifests itself on the local level in different forms. On the one hand, during elections: local, regional, national or European. On the other hand, in many forms of collective action by citizens who organize themselves in protest

movements, around opinion leaders in the public sphere, interest groups and NGOs. Often when there is a European dimension, the action starts at the local level. For that reason, it is important that citizens both understand their rights and that a more lively European public sphere emerges. As a result, we choose to develop teaching materials for secondary school pupils that contribute to the EU dimension of their civic competencies.

Five teaching packages have been developed:

1. Getting my rights: Europeanization at home
2. Lobbying and getting in touch with the EU
3. Organizing our interest
4. Travelling around
5. Advising the EU in solving Global Problems

The overall goal of these teaching packages is to teach secondary school pupils (aged 14 – 16/17) about EU citizenship. We want to focus on two aspects in particular:

1. EU citizenship is directly related to your daily life and you can benefit from it.
2. Choices made on the level of the EU affect your daily life and you can influence these choices, together with others close to you, as the EU is only five or less handshakes away from any EU citizen.

With these teaching packages we pursue three concrete goals. We want the pupils:

- a) to discover what rights they have as EU citizens, both during their daily life at home, and when traveling around;
- b) to develop the necessary competencies to get access to, realise and/or enforce their rights;
- c) to develop the civic and political competencies to participate in the variety of political communities on different levels they belong to in order to make their voices heard in decision-making on all levels.

This implies that the teaching packages depart from the perspective of the secondary school pupil in his or her daily life and local habitat.

The complete outline of the teaching packages is provided in Deliverable 11.6.

5. OTHER DISSEMINATION TOOLS

While drawing up the dissemination strategy for the bEUcitizen project, we realized that there are also other powerful tools to communicate academic results to the wider public, as short videos and visual art.

We actively looked into possibilities to work together with artists in order to engage in beyond the state of the art of the project's findings, in particular where tensions between various citizens' rights are concerned.

We worked together with Beatrice Ngalula Kabutakupua, journalist, producer and researcher in the field of migration from Africa, and with Circus Europe. This cooperation does not only make our research more accessible for the (Young) European citizen, it should also help Policy Makers in their understanding of the different tensions and barriers that are still persistent in the European citizenship.

VIDEOS

By the end of the project we will publish 5 short videos that address the challenges the EU and its citizens are facing. Each documentary uses a simplified language and approach in order to be understandable for a wider audience. The main characteristic of the produced video are of simplicity, clarity and entertainment.

1. [Insiders – Outsiders](#). This video focus on why the distinction between “Insiders” and “Outsiders” matters and on what the consequences of this distinction are.
2. [Gender & Generations](#)
3. [Brexit](#). This video tries to answer the questions on what led to the BREXIT vote and on its consequences for UK and EU citizens.
4. *Rivalry of Rights*. This video will show how certain citizenship rights conflict.
5. *Future scenarios of citizenship*. What could citizenship look like in 2030? 4 possible scenarios will be developed, looking into the future. This video will be based on the workshop “The future of Europe - Exploring strategies for strengthening EU Citizenship” and on the backstage of the bEUcitizen final conference.

CIRCUS EUROPE

Circus Europe is a project by visual artist Machteld van Buren and poet Peter van Lier.

In the large collection of collages “Circus Europe”, Machteld illustrates how the struggle for survival is being waged in various European countries. Some countries are depicted as an animal: the body consists of a map onto which the realistic head of an animal has been superimposed. Other countries are the playground for animals, performing acts that are indicative of how each nation functions. More information on Circus Europe can be found here: <http://circus-europe-exhibitions.blogspot.nl/>.

On Tuesday 30 July 2015 the exposition of Circus Europe was opened at the Zagreb Conference of bEUcitizen at the Faculty of Political Science of the University of Zagreb, from 29 June till 2 July 2015. During the opening session Hanneke van Eijken (Dutch poet and researcher of the bEUcitizen project), Peter van Lier (Dutch poet) and Ana Brnardić (poet from Croatia) read their poems inspired by Europe and the paintings of Europe made by Machteld van Buren (visual artist). The exhibition was open to visit during the whole conference and many researcher enjoyed the paintings and poems on Europe.

Collages of the Circus Europe art project will be hosted also at the bEUcitizen final conference (April 26-28, Brussels).

6. CONCLUSIONS

This Dissemination Report has provided the complete overview of the dissemination activities implemented in the scope of the bEUcitizen project, in accordance with the provisions of the Dissemination Plan and the Dissemination Strategy issued at the beginning of the project.

The achievements pointed out in the document show that the project has successfully disseminated its results and reached a high visibility within the scientific and political community. The effectiveness of dissemination activities has been ensured by defining appropriate target groups, allowing the most relevant audience to be reached with the most appropriate dissemination tools.

The main bEUcitizen dissemination instruments and activities include:

- a dedicated project website (www.beucitizen.eu) allowing for fast and easy communication of the most relevant information and news to a wide audience;
- a newsletter, which has been issued biannually during the project to inform relevant stakeholders about the key achievements and the next activities planned;
- a number of 7 Policy Briefs have been released during the project with the aim to spread policy scenarios and recommendations;
- a series of 5 teaching packages for secondary school pupils in the age group of 14-16/17, which will be distributed via the project website;
- public workshops and events have also been organized with the main purpose of communicating results, getting potential stakeholders directly involved in the work, but also for gathering feedback about the activities performed by the Consortium;
- representatives of the bEUcitizen Consortium have attended external public events presenting the activities performed and the results achieved by the project;

Furthermore, in order to reach a wider public in a more direct and easily understandable way, bEUcitizen cooperated with visual artist Machteld van Buren and with journalist and producer Beatrice Kabutakapua and made use of the visual arts to raise awareness and spark the debate on the current problems the European Union is facing.

Finally, the most relevant outcomes have been collected in a book series, which will be published in September 2017 by Edward Elgar Publishing, and will be presented during the Final Conference, to be held in Brussels on 26-28 April 2017.

ANNEXES – TABLE DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

COUNTRY	INSTITUTE	RESEARCHER	ACTIVITY	EVIDENCE	NOTES	TARGET GROUP
Period 1						
Austria	ESSHC Vienna	Patrick Wallis	Open Access? Guilds and Citizenship in Early Modern England, ESSHC Vienna, April 2014, Thursday 24 April 2014 14.00 - 16.00 Y-7 - SOC11 : Institutions of Exclusion? Guilds, Citizenship and Inequality in Early Modern Europe	draft PDF PPT presentation https://esshc.socialhistory.org/esshc-user/program/?network=0&textsearch=wallis	The ESSHC session was a panel organised on the topic of the project.	Historian and social scientists
Austria	Universität Innsbruck	Elena Ioriatti	Die Unionsbürgerschaft und die Förderung der grenz- und regionenüberschreitenden Mobilität durch die EU Prof. Elena Ioriatti, Universität Trient/MMag.Dr. Klaus Rier, Universität Innsbruck	program .doc	The bEUcitizen project was presented during the conference	Academic community
Austria	ESSHC Vienna	Maarten Prak	<i>Access to the Trade: Urban Craft Guilds and Social and Geographical Mobility in Early Modern Europe</i> , , ESSHC Vienna, April 2014, Thursday 24 April 2014 14.00 - 16.00, Y-7 - SOC11 : Institutions of Exclusion? Guilds, Citizenship and Inequality in Early Modern Europe	https://esshc.socialhistory.org/esshc-user/program?network=0&textsearch=Prak presentation PDF	The team working in WP3 has organised a session at the European Social Science History Congress in Vienna, in April 2014. Three of the four papers in the session were delivered by team members. In the core presentation, a first draft of the first deliverable, the project and its logo were explicitly mentioned, as shown in the accompanying slides. The session was scheduled on April 24, from 2-4 pm.	Historian and social scientists
Bosnia Herzegovina	CESI	Viktor Koska	Viktor Koska, 'Refugee status determination procedures in Croatia', CESI International Summer School on Refugee Law 21-28 July 2014, Sarajevo	PPT presentation http://www.cesi.fpn.unsa.ba/activities/report-on-cesi-international-	bEUcitizen was directly promoted during the presentation, also through the use of the official logo	activists, lawyers, students, NGO workers, anthropologists and practitioners from Europe,

				summer-school-on-refugee-law-21-28-july-sarajevo/#more-1647		Africa, and North America.
Croatia	UNIZG	Viktor Koska + Vedrana Baričević	Undergraduate course 'Croatian Politics, Actors and Processes' at the Faculty of Political Science, University of Zagreb.	syllabus of the course	The content of the course was structured around the topics and issues to be covered in the WPs 4 and 10.	Undergraduate students
Croatia		Viktor Koska	<i>Refugees, displaced person and citizens: the case of Croatian Serbs'</i> , University of Liverpool Europe and the World Centre. Yugoslavia Then and Now. Speakers: Viktor Kostka (University of Zagreb, Croatia) and Gezim Krasniqi (University of Edinburgh). - a Seminar event. 12th March 2014	PPT presentation	bEUcitizen was directly promoted during the presentation, also through the use of the official logo	Academic community, anyone interested in the topic
Croatia		Viktor Koska	Refugees, displaced person and citizens: the case of Croatian Serbs', The Challenges of Europe: The Quest for Citizenship (Inclusion and Exclusion in Contemporary European Societies) Dubrovnik, 7-11 April 2014	PPT presentation	bEUcitizen was directly promoted during the presentation, also through the use of the official logo	Masters and PhD students
	INTER UNIVERSITY CENTRE (IUC)	Wieger Bakker (UU)	Inclusion and Exclusion in Contemporary European Societies) Dubrovnik, 7-11 April 2014. Course Director	Course programme	bEUcitizen was directly promoted during the course	Masters and PhD students
Denmark	AAU	Birte Siim	International Workshop: Shifting Notions of Social Citizenship: The "Two Wests", June 11-12-13, 2014, Reid Hall, Paris, organized jointly by Prof. Alice Kessler-Harris/Columbia University – from bEUcitizen Advisory Board – and Maurizio Ferrera, University of Milan. Birte's talk was titled: <i>"The Challenge from Nationalism for European Citizenship and Democracy and the Potentials for Resistance from Transnational Civil Society."</i>	Paris CGC workshop programme	bEUcitizen was mentioned in Birte's presentation. Since there are not yet any research results from the bEUcitizen project, Birte referred to the research results from the previous EUROSHERE project, 6.EU framework	sociologists, political scientists, contemporary historians, and theorists of social policy
Denmark	UCPH	Ulla Neergaard	President FIDE Congress 2014	http://fide2014.eu/	Many of our researcher were present as discussant and rapporteurs.	Academic community, Policy makers
	AAU	Lise Rolandsen Augustin	The Othering of Domestic Violence: The EU and Cultural Framings of Violence against Women, Social Politics (Winter 2013) 20 (4):534-557.	doi: 10.1093/spp/jxt020	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	Academic community
Germany	GUF	Sandra Seubert	"Representative Government and Political Freedom", presented at the Internationale Mill-Konferenz, Bucerius Law School	.docx + programme Mill Conference	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the	Academic community

			Hamburg, 5-6 June 2014	+ Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	context of our project work	
Germany		Sandra Seubert	"Citizenship and Animal Rights", presented at the Conference of the Political Theory Section of the DVPW (German Political Science Association), University of Hamburg, 12-14 March 2014	.docx + Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic community
Germany	GUF	Daniel Gaus	"Demoi-kratie ohne Demos-kratie – welche Polity braucht eine demokratische EU?", presented at the Political Science Colloquium, University of Mainz, 29 January 2014	.docx Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic community
Germany		Daniel Gaus	"Demoi-cracy without Demos-cracy: What Polity for a Democratic EU?" at the conference "Europe, Democracy and Critical Theory. A German-Italian Workshop on Jürgen Habermas's Theory", Forschungskolleg Humanwissenschaften Bad Homburg/Germany, 4-6 December 2013	Programme + Demoi-cracy without dems-cracy – what polity for a democratic EU?.doc	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic community
		Daniel Gaus	Rational Reconstruction as a Method of Political Theory between Social Critique and Empirical Political Science, Constellations Volume 20, Issue 4, pages 553–570, December 2013	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/1/1467-8675.12064/full	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	Academic community
Hungary	CEU	Marie-Pierre Granger	20 September 2013 – Keynote speech – Dutch Association for Migration Research, Autumn meeting, Utrecht . Presentation: <i>'EU citizens and their civil rights - a blurred picture'</i> .	1. Speech PDF 2. DAMR meeting programme .doc	presentation which introduced the bEUcitizen project, in particular research to be carried out in WP7 and WP5.	Academic community
Italy	UNITN	Elena Ioriatti	INTEGRAZIONE E CITTADINANZA EUROPEA NEL CONTESTO DEL PLURILINGUISMO Una conversazione sui rapporti tra lingua e diritto in Europa (6 March 2014)	program PDF	Elena Ioriatti gave a talk about European citizenship, law and language and she made reference to bEUcitizen project, explaining the project itself and the current temporary results of the research	Academic community

Italy	UU	Trudie Knijn	<i>Life course transformations and citizenship: Gender and Generations.</i> Keynote lecture at the ESPAnet Italia conference 'Sfide alla cittadinanza e trasformazione dei corsi di vita: precarietà, invecchiamento e migrazioni', Turin, 18-20 September, 2014.	PPT presentation	bEUcitizen was directly promoted during the presentation, also through the use of the official logo.	Academic community
Norway	LSE	Isabel Shutes	"Market-based Citizenship, Work-related Conditionality and the Welfare Entitlements of Citizens and Non-citizens", European Social Policy Association (ESPAnet) annual conference, Oslo, 4-6 September 2014.	http://www.reassess.no/asset/7943/1/7943_1.pdf	Dissemination activity for WP10	Academic community
Poland	UJ	Marcin Wujczyk	THE HISTORY AND CURRENT DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL RIGHTS IN POLAND	PDF of part of the issue including article concerning our researches	the outcome of the research and the report for the 6 packages is published in the review Yearbook of Labour Law and Social Policy. The review is one of few national yearbook focused on labour law and social policy.	The review is read by most of labour law academics as well as practitioners interested in that filed
Sweden	Kommerskollegium, Stockholm	Sybe de Vries	Lecture 'Reconciling conflicting economic freedoms with fundamental rights', Stockholm, 29 November 2013 (Kommerskollegium)		acknowledgment bEUcitizen	
The Netherlands	UU	Trudie Knijn	<i>Varieties of Citizenship: barriers, tensions and dilemmas</i> , keynote lecture at the Conference 'In Search of European Political Union' Utrecht University, Utrecht, 19-21 June, 2014	PPT presentation	bEUcitizen was one of the topic of the presentation	Academic community
The Netherlands	UU	Mara Yerkes + Trudie Knijn	<i>Youth on the Move: tensions between EU and national level policies.</i> Paper presented at the 12th ESPAnet Conference "Beyond the Crisis in Europe - New Opportunities for reconciling sustainability, equality and economic robustness" Oslo, 4-6 September, 2014.	PPT presentation	bEUcitizen was directly introduced and promoted during the presentation, also through the use of the official logo	Academic community
The Netherlands	UU	Hanneke van Eijken	De Europese Unie & Europese burgers	PPT presentation	lecture given on European citizenship. Use of the logo in the presentation.	children between 8-11 years old
The Netherlands	UU	Hanneke van Eijken	DAMR Autumn meeting, 20 September 2013, Utrecht University	DAMR Programme	Conference organized for the Dutch Association for Migration Research, in which researcher of bEUcitizen were invited to speak about the first results of their research	Academic community

	UU	Hanneke van Eijken	Reference to bEUcitizen in her PhD Thesis: The Role of European Citizenship in the Constitutionalization of the European Union	http://www.europalawpublishing.com/EN/webshop/0/0/1/55171	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	
	UU	Hanneke van Eijken	Editorial for the European Gender Equality Law Review: 'European Citizenship, Gender Equality and Fundamental Rights: Different Paths or Coming to a Crossroads?'	http://ec.europa.eu/justice/gender-equality/files/law_reviews/egelr_2013_2_final_web_en.pdf	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	Academic community, policy makers, experts
	UU	Hanneke van Eijken	Article for the AB Jurisprudentie Bestuursrechtspraak	article in Word, published in October	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	Academic community, practitioners
The Netherlands	UU	Sybe de Vries	Presentatie seminar Toetreding EU tot het EVRM (samen met Dr. A. Buyse (Universiteit Utrecht), Mr. M. Fierstra (Hoge Raad) en Mr. R. Böcker (Min. BuZa), Utrecht, 25 juni 2013		acknowledgment bEUcitizen	
The Netherlands	UU	Sybe de Vries	Keynote seminar DAMR Autumn Meeting, All Rights Reserved? Barriers Towards European Citizenship (BEUCITIZEN), 20 September 2013	DAMR Programme	Conference organized for the Dutch Association for Migration Research, in which researcher of bEUcitizen were invited to speak about the first results of their research	Academic community
The Netherlands	UU	Sybe de Vries	Organization and presentation: Kick-Off meeting of the bEUcitizenship project with 26 universities and institutions (18-20 September 2013, Utrecht)			General public, policy makers and Academic community
The Netherlands	UU	Sybe de Vries	Presentaties in het kader van Instituten over het bEUcitizen-project (Utrecht)			Academic community
UK	University of Oxford	Sybe de Vries	Presentation: 'The Consumer Image in Free Movement Law', Congress, Oxford, 27-28 March 2014		acknowledgment bEUcitizen	Academic community
UK	University of Oxford	Sybe de Vries	Organization and presentation of the congress 'Five years Legally binding EU Charter', in collaboration with the Institute of European and Comparative Law, University of Oxford, May 9, 2014	Programme (http://beucitizen.eu/agenda/conference-five-years-legally-binding-eu-charter-of-fundamental-rights/)		Academic community
UK	LSE	Patrick Wallis	'Access to the trade: citizens, craft guilds and social and geographical mobility in early modern Europe', 2nd International symposium on quantitative historical research, Tsinghua University, China July 2014. (3-12 July 2014)	program PDF		Academic community

UK	Social Policy Association annual conference	Isabel Shutes	"'We're all Excluded Together': Work-related Conditionality and the Welfare Entitlements of Citizens and Non-Citizens", Social Policy Association annual conference, Sheffield, 14-16 July 2014.	http://socstudies.group.shef.ac.uk/spa/ConferenceProgOverview.pdf http://socstudies.group.shef.ac.uk/spa/SPAProgramme09072014.pdf	Dissemination activity for WP10	Academic community
UK	UOXF	Isabel Shutes	'We're all Excluded Together': Work-related Conditionality and the Welfare Entitlements of UK Citizens, EEA Citizens and Non-EEA Citizens", Centre on Migration Policy and Society, University of Oxford, 12 June 2014.	https://www.compas.ox.ac.uk/events/seminar-series/	Dissemination activity for WP10. Podcast available	Academic community
UK	UOXF	Sara Walker	Barriers to EU citizenship: insiders and outsiders in the context of the UK", Blog for Centre on Migration Policy and Society, University of Oxford, 2 September 2014.	http://compasoxfordblog.co.uk	Dissemination activity for WP10	Academic community, Policy makers
	UOXF	Elaine Chase, Martin Seeleib-Kaiser	Migration, EU Citizenship, and Social Europe - Essay in Social Europe Journal, 14/01/2014	http://www.social-europe.eu/2014/01/eu-citizenship-social-europe	Essay published in Social Journal Europe with reference to bEUcitizen	Academic community, Policy makers
		Cecilia Bruzelius, Elaine Chase, Cornelia Hueser and Martin Seeleib-Kaiser	The Social Construction of European Citizenship and Associated Social Rights – Working paper in Barnett Papers in Social Research, 2014: No 7	https://www.spi.ox.ac.uk/fileadmin/documents/PDF/Barnett_Paper_14-01.pdf	Working paper with acknowledgments to bEUcitizen	Academic community
UK	University of Glasgow	Daniel Gaus	Is democracy a coherent normative ideal for a democratic EU", presented at the ECPR General Conference, University of Glasgow, 3-6 September 2014	.docx + Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Political scientists
United States	Princeton University	Daniel Gaus	"Beyond the Systems Approach to Deliberative Democracy: Reconstructive Theory and the Epistemic Dimension of Democracy" at the conference "Epistemic Dimensions of Democracy Revisited: Normative and Empirical Perspectives", Princeton University, 30 April 2014.	.pdf + Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic community
Period 2						
Austria	ECPR	Wieger Bakker	ECPR Joint Sessions Workshop: Citizenship, Diversity, Participation and Education in Times of Change. Presentation "Education for European Citizenship and the Quest for a European Civic Culture. Towards a research design", 1-04-2015	Ppt presentation and paper		Academic community, students, field experts

Belgium	Europeans throughout the World (ETTW) and the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) in cooperation with the Latvian Presidency of the Council of the European Union	Sybe de Vries	Presentation: bEUcitizen Project at the Basic European Rights to Free Movement under Threat conference.	http://www.esc.europa.eu/?i=portal.en.events-and-activities-eu-free-movement http://www.esc.europa.eu/?i=portal.en.events-and-activities-eu-free-movement http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/Presentati onBrusselsEES CJan2015.pdf	Conference where in the Third Panel bEUcitizen coordinator Sybe de Vries participated on behalf of bEUcitizen under the theme "Combatting Scaremongering about Free Movement and Migration".	General public; politicians; policymakers; academic community
Canada	CRIDAQ.	Clara Isabel Velasco Rico	New Horizons: New Social Science Backgrounds.	Flyer and https://fr-fr.facebook.com/cridaq/photos/a.571437549623813.11273741831.11229088877997/571437629623805/	Seminar.	Academic community
Canada	ECPR	Uwe Puetter; Robert Csehi	ECPR General Conference, Montréal, Canada, 26-29 August, 2015.	http://ecpr.eu/Events/PanelDetails.aspx?PanelID=4430&EventID=94	Paper presented entitled: "Politicization and executive dominance in euro crisis decision-making: how Slovakia and Finland went from initial resistance to the approval of European rescue funds".	Academic community
Croatia	University of Zagreb	Wieger Bakker	Youth Side Event "Breaking Down Barriers: Future scenarios on youth and citizenship in 2030 – Youth and access to education, labor and political decision making".	http://beucitizen.eu/news/breaking-down-barriers-future-scenarios-on-youth-and-citizenship-in-2030-youth-and-access-to-education-labor-and-political-decision-making/	On the 29th of June, a group of 20 students and young professionals from Croatia, Slovenia and the Netherlands discussed different future scenarios for youth-citizenship. They analyzed and discussed the present situation and determined what they regard as	Students, young professionals

					important for youth. In addition, they looked at what different ways the European societies, and especially Croatia, might develop and which consequences these would involve. How could the world look in 2030?	
Croatia	bEUcitizen Conference	Uwe Puetter; Robert Csehi	bEUcitizen 2015 Open Mid-term Conference 'Being a citizen in Europe', Zagreb, Croatia, 29-30 June, 2015.	http://www.becitizen2015.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/PROGRAMME-Open-Conference-Website_updated.pdf	Paper presented under Stream 3 of the Open Conference entitled: "Euro crisis management in Slovakia and Finland – lessons for the practice of 'European political citizenship'".	Academic community
Croatia	bEUcitizen Conference	Wieger Bakker	Presentation "Breaking Down Barriers", Youth Side Event	Ppt presentation	29-06-2015	Students, young researchers
Croatia	Utrecht University; University of Zagreb.	Speakers: Prof. Sybe Vries; Machteld van Buren	Circus Europe's Art Exhibition in Zagreb.	http://circus-europe-exhibitions.blogspot.nl/	During the conference Being a citizen in Europe in Zagreb Circus Europe was exhibited at the Faculty of Political Science of the University of Zagreb from 29 June till 2 July 2015. Artist: Machteld van Buren; poets Hanneke van Eijken, Peter van Lier and Ana Brnardić.	Academic community; general public
Croatia	Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration. bEUcitizen 2015 Mid-Term Conference.	Margarita Argüelles Vélez; Carmen Benavides González; Silvia Gómez Ansón	Presentation "Constitutional protection of economic rights in EU member States".	http://www.becitizen2015.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/PROGRAMME-Open-Conference-Website_updated.pdf		Academic community
Croatia	Center for the Study of Ethnicity,	Raul Rodríguez Magdaleno;	Presentation "Nationals, Citizens, Long-Term Residents, Short-term Residents, playing havoc with	http://www.becitizen2015.eu/wp-		Academic community

	Citizenship and Migration. bEUcitizen 2015 Mid-Term Conference.	Davide De Pietri	traditional categories or building up new ones?".	content/uploads/2015/06/PROGRAMME-Open-Conference-Website_updated.pdf		
Croatia	Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration. bEUcitizen 2015 Mid-Term Conference.	Ángel Espiniella Menéndez; Pilar Jiménez Blanco	"Restrictions of the EU Citizens' Mobility: Preventing Social and Health Tourism".	http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/Jimenez-Blanco-Espiniella-Zagreb-Paper.pdf		Academic community
Croatia	Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration. bEUcitizen 2015 Mid-Term Conference.	Luis Antonio Fernández Villazón; Ana Rosa Argüelles Blanco	"Free movement of disabled people in the EU: The case of returned migrants to Spain".	http://beucitizen.eu/publications/free-movement-of-disabled-people-in-the-eu-the-case-of-returned-migrants-to-spain/		Academic community
Croatia		Josip Sipic	Blog entry: A year after the heteronormative marriage referendum in Croatia: outcomes and lessons learned.	http://beucitizen.eu/a-year-after-the-heteronormative-marriage-referendum-in-croatia-outcomes-and-lessons-learned/		Academic community; general public
Croatia	University of Zagreb, Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration.	Vedrana Baričević	Presentation and academic paper: Europeanization, "Citizenship and Belonging: Politics and Policies of Immigration and Citizenship in Croatia".	http://www.beucitizen2015.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/PROGRAMME-Open-Conference-Website_updated.pdf	Paper presentation at a scientific conference "Being a Citizen in Europe", organized by the University in Utrecht and the Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration (Zagreb, 29-30 June 2015); paper accepted to be published on the bEUcitizen webpage (stream 1).	Academic community; students
Croatia	Institute for Migration and Ethnic Studies.	Josip Šipić; Vedrana Baričević; Marina	Presentation: "Discursive Construction of Immigrant Community in the Croatian Media".	http://www.cedim.hr/scientific-conference-	Paper presentation at a scientific conference	Academic community; students; general public

		Matešić		migrations-and-ethnicity-at-the-beginning-of-the-21st-century/?lang=en	"Migration and Ethnicity at the beginning of the 21st century" organized by the Institute for Migration and Ethnic Studies (Zagreb, 26 February 2015).	
Croatia	European Parliament, Office for Information in the Republic of Croatia.	Vedrana Baričević	Presentation: "Development of asylum system and integration of refugees in Croatia".	http://www.europarl.hr/hr/programi_i_aktivnosti/javn-a-doga-anja/imigracij-etolerancija.html	Participation at the round table "Tolerance, diversity, immigration" organized by the European Parliament and the Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration (Zagreb, 8 May 2015).	Stakeholders, students; general public
Croatia	Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration. bEUcitizen 2015 Mid-Term Conference.	Vedrana Baričević	Presentation: "European asylum policies and protection of refugees".	http://www.cedim.hr/tribinu-i-okruglisto-izbjeglicka-kriza-i-politike-izbjeglicke-zastite-u-europskoj-uniji-i-hrvatskoj/	Presentation at the scientific conference "Refugee crisis in Europe and Croatia", organized by the Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration, Faculty of Political Science (Zagreb, 21 September 2015).	Academic community, stakeholders, students; general public
Croatia	European Parliament, Office for Information in the Republic of Croatia.	Vedrana Baričević	Presentation: "Refugee crisis and the future of the European Union".	http://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/hr/news-room/content/20151012AVI97162/html/Odr%C5%BEana-javna-debata-"Migracijska-kriza-i-budu%C4%87nost-europskog-projekta"	Participation at the round table "Migration crisis and the future of the European project" organized by the European Parliament, Office for Information in the Republic of Croatia (Zagreb, 9 October 2015).	Stakeholders, students; general public
Croatia	N1 TV.	Vedrana Baričević	Interview (daily news)	http://hr.n1info.com/a75649/Vijesti/Izbjeglice-bi-se-mogle-vracati-u-Hrvatsku-i-Madjarstvu		General public

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Croatia	H-alter.	Vedrana Baričević	Interview on media representation of the refugees in Croatia (article "Stručnjaci analiziraju krizu u Hrvatskoj").			
Croatia	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political Science, Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration.	Josip Šipić	Presentation: "WP9: Balancing Gender and Generational Citizenship"	Presentation; https://vimeo.com/122724479	Presentation of WP 9 activities at the official "Opening of the Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration and Presentation of FP7 project bEUcitizen" (23 January 2015).	Academic community; university students; general public
Croatia	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political Science, Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration.	Josip Šipić	Blog entry: "A year after the heteronormative marriage referendum in Croatia: outcomes and lessons learned".	http://beucitizen.eu/a-year-after-the-heteronormative-marriage-referendum-in-croatia-outcomes-and-lessons-learned/		Academic community; general public
Croatia	European Parliament, Office for Information in the Republic of Croatia.	Josip Šipić	Presentation: "Media Coverage of Immigration in Croatia".	http://www.europarl.hr/hr/programi_i_aktivnosti/javnostna-događanja/imigracijetolerancija.html	Participation at the round table "Tolerance, diversity, immigration" organized by the European Parliament, Office for Information in the Republic of Croatia (Zagreb, 8 May 2015).	General public
Croatia	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political Science, Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration.	Viktor Koska	Presentation: "bEUcitizen project".	Presentation: https://vimeo.com/122724479 http://www.beucitizen2015.eu/	Presentation of bEUcitizen WPs activities at the official "Opening of the Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration and Presentation of FP7 project bEUcitizen" (23 January 2015).	General Public, Academic Community
Croatia	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political Science, Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship	Viktor Koska; Josip Šipić; Ana Matan	Official opening of the Centre for the Study of ethnicity, citizenship and migration (CEDIM) and the public presentation of the FP7 project bEUcitizen (23.1.2015).	https://web.facebook.com/cedimhr/photos/pb.1537402743169018.-2207520000.1450428319./1554409204801705/?type=3		General Public, Academic Community

	and Migration.			&theater, Presentation; https://vimeo.com/122724479,		
Croatia	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political Science, Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration.	Viktor Koska; Danijela Anticic-Lovic; Vedrana Baricevic; Josip Sipić	BEUCITIZEN 2015 Mid-Term Conference, Being a citizen in Europe , 29-30 June 2015	http://www.beucitizen2015.eu/ , https://vimeo.com/147012000	Mid Term conference is one of the main dissemination activities of the project bEUcitizen. With more than 150 participant, activities of bEUcitizen have been presented to wider general public. The video has been broadcasted on the Croatian National Television.	General Public, Academic community
Croatia	tportal.hr (online portal.	Viktor Koska	Interview for the Croatian online portal: Što sve (dobro i loše) trebamo znati o izbjegličkoj krizi? (What do we have to know (good or bad) about the refugee crisis? (26.9.2015).	http://www.tportal.hr/vijesti/hrvatska/397923/Sto-sve-trebamo-dobro-i-lose-znati-o-izbjeglickoj-krizi.html		General Public
Croatia	H-alter.org, online portal.	Viktor Koska	Intervju: Wanted and unwanted foreigners. (17.12.2014)	http://www.h-alter.org/vijesti/pozeljni-i-nepozeljni-stranci	Intervju on refugees and foreigners in Croatia, in which activities of the bEUcitizen project have been presented to the general public.	General public
Croatia	Telegram (newspaper).	Vedrana Baričević	Comment on Croatian asylum policies (article "Ovo je Celestine, naš najnoviji sugrađanin. Jedan je od samo 3% ljudi koji dobiju azil u Hrvatskoj"; by Jelena Tešija, 16 June 2015).	http://www.telegram.hr/price/ovo-je-celestine-nas-najnoviji-sugradanin-jedan-je-od-samo-3-ljudi-koji-dobiju-azil-u-hrvatskoj/		General public
Croatia	Jutarnji list (newspaper).	Vedrana Baričević	Interview on Refugee crisis and Croatian asylum and migration policies (article "Stručnjaci analiziraju krizu u Hrvatskoj", 18 September 2015).	http://www.jutarnji.hr/analiza-migracijskih-strucnjaka/1420190/		General public
Croatia	Croatian Radio and Television.	Vedrana Baričević and Viktor	Interview on Refugee crisis, Croatian asylum politics and policies and integration (broadcast "Isti i različiti,	http://mojtv.hr/kanal/tv-program/158/		General public

		Koska	by Danja Dubravac, 23 September 2015).	hrvatski-radio-1/2015-09-23/emisija/70678352/isti-i-razliciti.aspx		
Croatia	University of Zagreb		Official website of Center for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration (CEDIM) is a newly established center at the Faculty of Political Science in Zagreb, Croatia.	http://www.cedim.hr/ https://web.facebook.com/cedimhr/	Official website of CEDIM Centre, which is the main dissemination outcome of the project for Zagreb team (without bEUcitizen, we would not have the Centre, and the Centre became one of the leading institutions for migration and citizenship in Croatia).	Academic community; university students; general public
Czech Republic	Masaryk University.	Vít Hloušek	Presentation: bEUcitizen Project's WPs 4 and 8, seminar on MU participation.	Presentation	Serie of brief seminars for PhD students and academic staff at the faculty.	University students; academic community
		Vit Hloušek	Blog entry: European citizenship and failures of euro-optimistic politicians.	http://beucitizen.eu/european-citizenship-and-failures-of-euro-optimist-politicians/		Academic community; general public
Denmark	CESEL; RENFORCE	Silvia Adamo; Sybe de Vries; Hanneke van Eijken; Elena Ioriatti; Catherine Jacqueson	bEUcitizen International Research Seminar: EU-Citizenship and Rights	Program	bEUcitizen International Research Seminar: EU-Citizenship and Rights, in collaboration with University of Utrecht's research group RENFORCE (Centre for Regulation and Enforcement of Europe), Copenhagen, 11 December 2014 (organisation and steering Ulla Neergaard, Catherine Jacqueson, Silvia Adamo) (WP5, WP7).	General public; academic community
Denmark	Copenhagen University	Hanneke van Eijken	Speech on the Protection of Fundamental Rights: The Composite Citizen in the European Union.	Program	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community
Denmark	Copenhagen	Hanneke	Organization Conference EU	Program	Logo of	Academic

	University	van Eijken	citizenship and rights.		bEUcitizen.	community
Denmark	University of Copenhagen.	Silvia Adamo	Lunch Talk, Prof. Carlos Closa Montero (EUI): Are we alone in the universe? Placing EU citizenship among other forms of supranational citizenship and rights in regional integration organizations.	Program	Lunch Talk, Faculty of Law, University of Copenhagen, 19 May 2015 (organisation and steering Silvia Adamo) (WP7).	Academic community
Denmark	University of Copenhagen.	Ulla Neergaard	Lecture on union citizenship	Presentation	Lecture, Union Citizenship I (Notion and Rights) [Forelæsning 16, Unionsborgerskab (Begreb og rettigheder)], 23 and 28 April 2015 (Ulla Neergaard) (WP5, WP6, WP7).	Students
Denmark	University of Copenhagen.	Catherine Jacqueson	EURECO-lecture, 'Revisiting welfare tourism – What are the challenges?'	Presentation	EURECO-lecture, 'Revisiting welfare tourism – What are the challenges?' 18 November 2014 (Catherine Jacqueson), University of Copenhagen (WP6).	Students
Denmark	University of Copenhagen.	Catherine Jacqueson	Presentation: 'The Court of Justice and Welfare Tourism', bEUcitizen International Research Seminar: EU-Citizenship and Rights.	Presentation	Presentation: 'The Court of Justice and Welfare Tourism', bEUcitizen International Research Seminar: EU-Citizenship and Rights, University of Copenhagen, 11 December 2014 (Catherine Jacqueson) (WP6).	Academic community; students
Denmark	University of Copenhagen.	Silvia Adamo	Lecture: Integration Law in Denmark and EU – Right to Integration, or Duty to Integrate?	Presentation	Lecture, Centre for Advanced Migration Studies, MA Course: International Migration. University of Copenhagen, 13 April 2015 (Silvia Adamo) (WP7).	MA students
Denmark	University of Copenhagen.	Silvia Adamo	Lecture: The State and Migration – A View from Law and Justice.	Presentation	Lecture, Centre for Advanced Migration Studies, MA	MA students

					Course: International Migration. University of Copenhagen, 26 November 2014 (Silvia Adamo) (WP7).	
	University of Copenhagen.	Ulla Neergaard	Blog entry: The XXVI FIDE Congress in Copenhagen, 2014, regarding Union Citizenship and other important EU topics.	http://beucitizen.eu/the-xxvi-fide-congress-in-copenhagen-2014-regarding-union-citizenship-and-other-important-eu-topics	Neergaard, U., Blog entry: The XXVI FIDE Congress in Copenhagen, 2014, regarding Union Citizenship and other important EU topics, 12 June 2014 (WP5, WP6, WP7).	Academic community; interested students; general public
	University of Copenhagen.	Dean Hartley; Catherine Jacqueston	Medical treatment in the EU - a right for the few?: Denmark's strained relationship with patients' freedom of movement.	http://research.ku.dk/search/?pure=en/publications/sygdomsbehandling-i-eu-en-ret-for-de-faa(8676ad20eb7a-4d73-a05d-69ec8d13bba2).html	Hartlev, M. and Jacqueston, C. (2014), Sygdomsbehandling i EU - en ret for de få?: Danmarks anstrengte forhold til patienters fri bevægelighed, 6 Juristen December 2014, pp. 191-202 (WP6).	Academic community; students
	University of Copenhagen.	Catherine Jacqueson; Katarina Hylten-Cavallius	Blog entry : When benefit tourism enters the Court-room – The consequences of the Dano-case.	http://beucitizen.eu/when-benefit-tourism-enters-the-court-room-the-consequences-of-the-dano-case	Jacqueson, C. and Hylten-Cavallius, K., Blog entry : When benefit tourism enters the Court-room – The consequences of the Dano-case, 26 January 2015 (WP6).	Academic community; interested students; general public
	University of Copenhagen.	Silvia Adamo	Blog entry: Studying Abroad with Benefits from 'Home': the Martens Judgement.	http://beucitizen.eu/studying-abroad-with-benefits-from-home-the-martens-judgement	Adamo, S., Blog entry: Studying Abroad with Benefits from 'Home': the Martens Judgement, 23 March 2015 (WP5).	Academic community; interested students; general public
Denmark	Aalborg University.	Lise Rolandsen Agustín	Lecture on Employment and Social Policies.	Course Program	Course on EU Policies and European Political Economy. Included examples from BEUcitizen.	MA students
Estonia	University of Tartu.	Gaabriel Tavits	Blog entry: Citizenship – VIP card for a prosperous life?	http://beucitizen.eu/citizenship-vip-card-for-a		Academic community; general public

				prosperous-life/		
Estonia	University of Tartu.	Gaabriel Tavits	February - April 2015, lectures about the social security law.	Course program	Free movement of persons in EU, social rights in Estonia (social assistance, health insurance).	master students; bachelor students
Estonia	University of Tartu.	Gaabriel Tavits	Advanced training for Eures advisers about the EU social security and labour law.	Presentation	Free movement of persons in EU, social rights in EU.	Eures advisers; trade union members
France	Council for European Studies.	Uwe Puetter; Robert Csehi	22nd International Conference of Europeanists organized by the Council for European Studies in Paris, France, 8-10 July, 2015.	https://ces.cofnfx.com/ces/2015/webprogram/Session4479.html	Paper presented entitled: 'Political choice and constraints imposed by financial markets – understanding the nexus of national executives, parliaments, and citizens in European Union decision-making at times of crisis'.	Academic community
Germany	University of Bayreuth (Forschungsstelle für Verbraucherecht) and bEUcitizen.	Christoph Strünck; Frans van Waarden	Conference 'In the Name of Consumers? Public Interest Litigation in Europe' .	http://www.verbraucherrecht.uni-bayreuth.de/pdf_ordner/Taung-Rechtsdrucksatzung-Flyer-DIN-lang-Wickelfalz-6-Seiten.pdf	Strünck opened the conference with a lecture on 'Collective Legal Aid in Consumer Policy' and concluded the conference. Van Waarden gave a presentation on 'Public Interest Litigation: Tensions between Democracy and the Rule of Law'.	Academics; lawyers; interest groups; notably representatives of Consumer Interest Associations
Germany	University of Heidelberg.	Frans van Waarden	Symposium on 'Knowledge and Institutions' by Economic Geographers.	http://knowledgeandspace.uni-hd.de/symposia/institutions/s13_program.html	Presentation on 'Institutions, Time, and Territory: Path Dependent Institutional Development within Geographic Boundaries'.	Interdisciplinary academic community
Germany	University of Siegen.	Christoph Strünck	On behalf of the consumer? Collective redress in Europe. Writings on consumer law and consumer sciences.	http://www.jww.de/index.php?page=detail&id=171	bEUcitizen mentioned in introductory chapter.	Academic community; policymakers
		Olga Sendetska	Blog entry: In the name of consumers? Public interest litigation in Europe.	http://beucitizen.eu/in-the-name-of-consumers-public-		Academic community; general public

				interest-litigation-in-europe/		
		Brigitte Unger	Blog entry: Hanna in luck.	http://beucitizen.eu/hanna-in-luck/		Academic community; general public
Germany	Goethe University Frankfurt.	Sandra Seubert	Presentation of Sandra Seubert on "Antinomies of European Citizenship" at the international conference "The Changing Nature of Citizenship".	Program		Scientists
Germany	Goethe University Frankfurt.	Sandra Seubert	Presentation of Sandra Seubert on "European Citizenship: Prospects and Challenges".	Program	Presentation at the conference "Performing Citizenship", Kulturwissenschaftliches Institut Essen, Germany.	Scientists; Practitioners
Germany	Goethe University Frankfurt.	Sandra Seubert; Daniel Gaus	University seminar by Daniel Gaus and Sandra Seubert on "Europäische Bürgerschaft – Die politische Verfassung der EU im Lichte aktueller Citizenship-Debatten".	Program	Goethe-Universität Frankfurt, Germany, winter term 2014/2015.	Students
Hungary	Central European University and bEUcitizen.	Marie-Pierre F. Granger	A dissemination event for the bEUcitizen project, WP7 focused on the exercise and enforcement of civil rights in Hungary.	Program		Lawyers from the main civil/human rights groups promoting and defending civil rights in Hungary
Hungary	School of Public Policy Center for European Union Research French Institute of Budapest.	Marie-Pierre F. Granger	Series of Discussion Panels: Reflecting on Freedom(s), Religion, and Security.	http://spp.ceu.edu/events/2015-05-19/lapres-charlie-reflecting-freedom-religion-and-security	This event takes place in the context of research activities carried out under the EU-funded bEUcitizen.	Academic community
Hungary	Center for European Union Research (Central European University) and Lendulet-HPOs Research Group (Hungarian Academy of Science).		Conference: 'Hungarian Particularism in the European Union: Politico-Legal Perspectives'.	Overview: https://ceur.ceu.edu/events/2015-05-15/hungarian-particularism-in-the-european-union-politico-legal-perspectives Program: https://ceur.ceu.edu/sites/default/files/field_attachment/event/node-43346/prog15maymtaceurnew.pdf		

Hungary	Central European University and bEUcitizen.	Uwe Puetter; Robert Csehi	Ivan Mikloš, the former Slovakian Finance Minister gave a talk about his role in managing the euro crisis decisions in Slovakia between 2010 and 2012.	https://ceur.eu.edu/news/2015-02-03/talk-by-ivan-miklos-former-slovakian-finance-minister	In his talk, Mikloš commented on Slovakian parliamentary politics in relation to major euro crisis decision-making and thus the access of citizens to EU-related decision-making processes. The event was intended to demonstrate the policy relevance of the research activities in WP8.	Open event for students; academics; journalists
Hungary	Center for European Union Research (Central European University) and Center for Policy Studies (CEU).	Katalin Amon	Presentation at the workshop “Care chain: care regimes, migration and gender equality in an enlarged Europe” at Central European University.	https://cps.eu.edu/events/2015-01-26/care-chain-care-regimes-migration-and-gender-equality-in-an-enlarged-europe		Academic community
Hungary	European Commission, European Network for Gender Equality (ENEGE).	Andrea Krizsan	Report: Dignity, integrity and ending gender violence in the European Union.	http://enege.eu/sites/default/files/13-Andrea-Krizsan.pdf		Policymakers
Hungary	Center for European Union Research (Central European University).	Andrea Krizsan; Katalin Amon	Blog entry: Egalitarian euroskepticism: how does the Hungarian extreme right contribute to ideas of European citizenship?	http://beucitizen.eu/egalitarian-euroskepticism-how-does-the-hungarian-extreme-right-contribute-to-ideas-of-european-citizenship/		General public
Hungary	Central European University.	Marie-Pierre Granger; Orsolya Salat	Presented at the bEUcitizen 2015 Annual Conference in Zagreb, entitled ‘In need of an EU civil rights’ movement? Overcoming the weakness of EU citizenship as a legal concept’.	Presentation		Academic community
Hungary	Central European University.	Marie-Pierre Granger; Orsolya Salat	Reached out to Jackson Oldfield, from the civil society organization European Alternative, who organized, together with the Hungarian Europe Society, a training on EU citizenship and discussion on What can we do to	Communication exchange	12 October 2015: Marie-Pierre Granger and Orsolya Salat (CEU) reached out to Jackson Oldfield, from the	

			create a Europe of rights and values?		civil society organization European Alternative, who organized, together with the Hungarian Europe Society, an training on EU citizenship and discussion on What can we do to create a Europe of rights and values? The event took place in Budapest on 17 October 2015. EA is interested in the project and we will examine further cooperation. Perhaps they could be invited to the GA in Oviedo in June 2015.	
Hungary	Central European University.	Orsolya Salat	Blog entry: Anxiety's delays in Europe – An East-West Travel Diary.	http://beucitizen.eu/anxietys-delays-in-europe-an-east-west-travel-diary/		Academic community; interested students; general public
Hungary	Central European University.	Marie-Pierre Granger	Blog entry: All sisters in tears – my right to be treated equally badly.	http://beucitizen.eu/all-sisters-in-tears-my-right-to-be-treated-equally-badly		Academic community; interested students; general public
Hungary	Central European University.	Orsolya Salat	Blog entry: Long months unfinished journey into the dark – the refugee crisis'.	http://beucitizen.eu/long-months-unfinished-journey-into-the-dark-the-refugee-crisis-from-budapest/		Academic community; interested students; general public
Hungary	CEU Center for European Union Research and the bEUcitizen project.	Orsolya Salat; Marie-Pierre Granger	Roundtable discussion organized by the CEU Center for European Union Research and the bEUcitizen project which brought together representatives of civil society organizations active in the protection and defense of civil rights in Hungary.	Program	Orsolya Salat and Marie-Pierre Granger presented the research carried out in the project and in particular in WP7 on civil rights, and participants then engaged in presentations and	Academic community

					discussions on the effective exercise and enforcement of civil rights, reliance on EU law in litigation and lobbying activities in support of EU rights, and particular legal, procedural, financial, political, institutional, professional or another other types of obstacles which citizens, and NGOs that support them, face when they seek to enforce civil rights.	
Hungary	Center for European Union Research of CEU, the CEU School of Public Policy, the French Institute and French Embassy in Budapest.	Marie-Pierre Granger	A series of panel discussions examining important challenges resulting from the January 2015 terrorist attacks in Paris.	Program	Marie-Pierre Granger (CEU) organized a series of panel discussions examining important challenges resulting from the January 2015 terrorist attacks in Paris. External academic participants as well as practitioners debated, in the context of three roundtables, discussed from a variety of perspectives (law, political sciences, sociology, policy, philosophy, and journalism) the impact of the attacks and policy reactions to them, including on the exercise of core civil rights, such as freedom of expression, media freedom, privacy and freedom of movement.	Academic community
Hungary		Robert	Blog entry: How financial market	http://beuciti		Academic

		Csehi	pressure constrains political citizenship – lessons from euro crisis decision-making in Slovakia.	zen.eu/how-financial-market-pressure-constrains-political-citizenship-lessons-from-euro-crisis-decision-making-in-slovakia/		community; general public
Hungary		Andrea Krizsan	Blog entry: Egalitarian Euroscepticism? How does the Hungarian extreme right contribute to ideas of European Citizenship?	http://beucitizen.eu/egalitarian-euroscepticism-how-does-the-hungarian-extreme-right-contribute-to-ideas-of-european-citizenship/		Academic community; general public
Ireland	Newstalk Radio.	Graham Finlay	Interview regarding Refugee Resettlement.	http://www.newstalk.com/podcasts/Moncrieff/History_on_The_Moncrieff_Show/105283/	Acknowledgement bEUcitizen.	General public
Israel		Dana Halevy	Blog entry: Equal rights for diverse family forms: the case of surrogacy in Israel.	http://beucitizen.eu/equal-rights-for-diverse-family-forms-the-case-of-surrogacy-in-israel/		Academic community; general public
Israel	Hebrew University of Jerusalem.	David Levi-Faur	Presentation at a conference on the ethics of privatization.	http://mishkenot.org.il/events_ethic	Presentation on regulatory capitalism, citizenship and credit market reforms.	General public; politicians; policymakers; academic community
Israel	Hebrew University of Jerusalem.	David Levi-Faur	Presentation at a Seminar on Social Policy at the School of Social Welfare.	http://publicpolicy.huji.ac.il/	Seminar.	Academic community
Israel	Hebrew University of Jerusalem.	David Levi-Faur	Presentation at the Israeli Democracy Institute on financial citizenship: privacy and equality aspects.	http://www.idi.org.il	Round table, lunch box presentation.	Think tank presentation
Israel	Hebrew University of Jerusalem.	David Levi-Faur	Public presentations at the Economics Committee of the Parliament on the collection, ranking and commodification of financial data.	http://main.knesset.gov.il/Activity/committees/Economics/Pages/CommitteeTVarchive.aspx	Formal meetings of the economics committee.	Legislators
Italy	State University of Milan.	Manuela Naldini; Joelle Long	Conference "Freedom of movement and legal recognition of families".	http://www.diritto pubblico.unimi.it/ecm/	Manuela Naldini and Joelle Long introduced	University students; academic

				home/aggiornamenti-e-archivi/tutte-le-notizie/content/liberazione-e-riconoscimento-delle-famiglie-profilo-di-diritto-internazionale-privato-tutela-dei-diritti-e-ordinamento-interno.0000.UNIMIDIRE-38827	bEUcitizen and presented a paper on "same sex marriage tourism and procreative tourism". The paper was written within the research they are carrying out within task 9.8 of WP9.	community
Italy	Trento Faculty of Law	Elena Ioriatti	Cittadinanza e lingua nell'Unione europea.	Presentation	Presentation of the bEUcitizen program on the occasion of the seminar.	Academic community
Italy	Trento Faculty of Law.	Elena Ioriatti	La vendita internazionale: prospettive e problemi, April 2015,	Presentation	Presentation by Elena Ioriatti and acknowledgment bEUcitizen (training of young lawyers, organised by prof. avv. Elena Ioriatti as member of the Trento Bar school of law).	Academic community; lawyers
Italy	Trento Faculty of Law.	Paolo Guarda	"Consortium Agreement and Intellectual Property Rights within the European Union Research and Innovation Programme".	Presentation	Presentation by Paolo Guarda and acknowledgment bEUcitizen at the International Seminar on "New Perspective of Copyright in Europe: Harmonization, Territoriality and New Technologies", Bocconi University, Milano, November, 14, 2014.	Academic community
Italy	Trento Faculty of Law.	Elena Ioriatti	Workshop on the legal translation of EU law" (April 2015).	Presentation	Presentation by Elena Ioriatti and acknowledgment bEUcitizen.	Academic community
Italy		Joelle Long	Blog entry: Promoting Children as Active Citizens: the Role of Legal Clinics.	http://beucitizen.eu/promoting-children-		Academic community; general public

				as-active-citizens-the-role-of-legal-clinics/		
Italy		Flavio Guella	Blog entry: EU rights for workers and their possible prevalence on Member States financial interests.	http://beucitizen.eu/eu-rights-for-workers-and-their-possible-prevalence-on-member-states-financial-interests/		Academic community; general public
Italy	IMISCOE-European University Institute.	Monica Ferrin	Paper presented: "Strengthening Limits to Mobility? The Economic Crisis and EU Citizens' Mobility".	http://www.eu.eu/Projects/TheForum/Events/MobilityinCrisis.aspx	Paper presented at the conference Mobility in Crisis: Is Europe becoming more mobile during the economic crisis or is European mobility in crisis?	Academic community
Italy	Collegio Carlo Alberto is a joint venture of the Compagnia di San Paolo and the University of Torino.	Monica Ferrin	Paper presented: "Strengthening Limits to Mobility? The Economic Crisis and EU Citizens' Mobility".	http://www.carloalberto.org/events/seminars/politics-and-society/2015-2016	Paper presented during the conference "Seminars in Politics and Society".	Academic community
Japan	Kyoto Conference Center, XVIIth World Economic History Congress.	Bert De Munck; Chris Minns; Maarten Prak; Patrick Wallis	Session with papers from the project, August 7, 2015.	http://www.whoehc2015.org/programmeoverview.html	Papers presented by Chris Minns, Maarten Prak, Patrick Wallis, comment by Bert De Munck.	Academic community
Poland	Jagiellonian University.	Marcin Wujczyk	Presentation at the Labour Law Discussion Group, Oxford University.	https://www.law.ox.ac.uk/content/protection-interpretation-how-labour-rights-are-protected-european-committee-social-rights	BEUcitizen project mentioned during the lecture.	Academic community; university students
Slovenia	International Public Administration. Faculty of Administration, University of Ljubljana.	Alejandra Boto Álvarez	Article "Unsolved Questions Regarding EU Citizens Access to Public Healthcare Services in Spain".	https://www.google.es/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0ahUKEwi6kq3r9KJJAhVJwBQKHVz7BfQQFgghMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fuprava.fu.uni-		

				lj.si%2Findex.php%2FIPAR%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2F299%2Fpdf_17&usg=AFQjCN GkZ2fe98Je_Q ps7MTOcJFc VhQFQ&sig2=_1E7uDcWWe wt9DorkRRp7 w&cad=rja		
Spain	Institut D'estudis Autonomics (Government of Catalonia) and bEUcitizen project.	Clara I. Velasco Rico; Sybe de Vries; Francis Cheneval; Frans van Waarden	Joint seminar: Current Topics in European Citizenship.	http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/CURRENT-TOPICS-IN-EUROPEAN-CITIZENSHIP.pdf	Joint seminar co-organized by bEUcitizen and the Government of Catalonia to discuss an array of topics covered in various WPs in relation to European Citizenship.	Academics; diplomats or civil servants working on issues related to European citizenship; interested graduate students and politicians and civil servants
Spain	IBEI.	Jacint Jordana; Francis Cheneval; Andrea C. Bianculli	A roundtable on 'National identities and European Citizenship: A legitimacy conflict?'	Flyer and advertisement published in Catalan newspaper; http://beucitizen.eu/agenda/national-identities-and-european-citizenship-a-legitimacy-conflict	Panelists discussed what we can expect from the European political citizenship, and whether barriers can prevent identity and national consolidation.	Academics; diplomats or civil servants working on issues related to European citizenship; interested graduate students
Spain	Max-Planck-Institute for Social Law and Social Policy and the University of Manchester.	Maribel González Pascual	Workshop "Migration, Free Movement and Portability of Social Rights".	Program	Maribel Gonzalez Pascual presented on "Freedom of movement and the portability of social rights within the European Union".	Academics
Spain		Maribel González Pascual	Summer course "Fundamental Rights and Judicial Protection".	Program	Maribel Gonzalez Pascual presented on "Fundamental Rights Protection and Judicial Cooperation in Criminal Matter".	LLMM students and academics.
Spain	UACES.	Uwe Puetter; Robert Csehi	UACES 45th Annual Conference, Bilbao, Spain, 7-9 September, 2015	http://uaces.org/documents/events/Bilbao/A-Z%20Research%20Programme%202015-08-19.pdf	Paper presented entitled: 'Euro-crisis decision-making in Slovakia and Finland: the interplay of technocratic elites,	Academic community

					governments, and parliamentary scrutiny'.	
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo.	Leopoldo Tolivar Alas	Blog entry : "A noteworthy aspect of the Right to housing".	http://beuciti.zen.eu/a-noteworthy-aspect-of-the-right-to-housing/		Academic community; interested students; general public
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo.	Ana Rosa Argüelles Blanco	Blog entry : "Mobility and inequality in the enjoyment of social rights".	http://beuciti.zen.eu/mobility-and-inequality-in-the-enjoyment-of-social-rights/		Academic community; interested students; general public
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo.	Carmen Benavides González	Blog entry : "Comparison of United Nations and European Union Economic rights".	http://beuciti.zen.eu/comparison-of-united-nations-and-european-union-economic-rights/		Academic community; interested students; general public
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo.	Luis Antonio Fernández Villazón	Blog entry : "Vulnerable Citizens in the EU, a border line between Policies and Law".	http://beuciti.zen.eu/vulnerable-citizens-in-the-eu-a-border-line-between-policies-and-law/		Academic community; interested students; general public
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo.	Javier Andrés González Vega	Blog entry: Some views from Kirchberg: The Big Bang theory and the third man (or the growing distance between Luxembourg and Strasbourg...and individuals too"	http://beuciti.zen.eu/some-views-from-kirchberg-the-big-bang-theory-and-the-third-man-or-the-growing-distance-between-luxembourg-and-strasbourg-and-individuals-too/		Academic community; interested students; general public
Spain		Carmen Benavides González	Blog entry: Comparison of United Nations and European Union Economic rights.	http://beuciti.zen.eu/comparison-of-united-nations-and-european-union-economic-rights/		Academic community; general public
Spain		Clara Isabel Velasco Rico	Blog entry: A reflection on European citizenship from a Catalan perspective.	http://beuciti.zen.eu/a-reflection-on-european-		Academic community; general public

				citizenship-from-a-catalan-perspective/		
Spain	Revista Vasca de Administració n Pública.	Miriam Cueto Pérez	Article "Crisis económica y Administración Pública".	http://www.ehu.eus/documents/1582124/4168298/Demetrio+Lopereña+Rota+I+n+memoriam.pdf		
Spain	Institut d'Estudis Autònoms e Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona.	Flavio Guella	Presentation "A territorial fiscal citizenship: public expenditure differentiation and equal protection of rights in Europe".	-	Presentation during the meeting "Current topics in European citizenship" in May 2015.	Academic community
Spain	Abad Castelos, M., (ed.) Cuadernos Gregorio Peces Barba.	Javier Andrés González Vega	Article: "Revisitando el concepto de Minoría: Derecho internacional, Derecho europeo y práctica española (A propósito de la aplicación del Convenio Marco para la protección de las Minorías Nacionales)".	http://www.researchgate.net/publication/272174130_REVISITANDO_EL_CONCEPTO_DE_MINORIA_A_DERECHO_INTERNACIONAL_DERECHO_EUROPEO_Y_PRCTICA_ESPAOLA*_%28A_proposito_de_la_aplicacion_del_Convenio_Marco_para_la_proteccion_de_las_Minorias_Nacionales%29	Article in press.	Academic community
Sweden	Department of Law, University of Gothenburg.	Sara Stendahl	Organized a seminar on free legal counseling as a way to better health, including discussions on local initiatives for destitute EU-citizens.	http://law.handels.gu.se/digitalAssets/1508/1508878_glocal-health2.pdf	Presentation by Sara Stendahl on the bEUcitizen-project and how to make use of the research results from the project in local initiatives.	Academic community; general public
Sweden		Otto Swedrup	Participated in a panel organized by the Swedish Institute for European Policy Studies and The Swedish ESF (European Social Fund) Council.	http://www.esf.se/sv/Vara-fonder/FEAD/	Presentation by Otto Swedrup on the bEUcitizen-project to a newly created network of researchers working with projects regarding EU-citizens. (Program the meeting cited under "Evidence" is unfortunately	Academic community; policymakers

					only in Swedish.)	
Sweden		Otto Swedrup	Participated in the conference "Destitute EU-citizens" organized by Gotheburg Rescue Mission.	http://utsattaumedborgar.e.se ; https://twitter.com/ottoswede/status/649556425853784064	Presentation by Otto Swedrup on the situation for migrating EU-citizens in Sweden, including information on the bEUcitizen-project.	General public; politicians; policymakers; academic community
Sweden	Department of Law, University of Gothenburg.	Otto Swedrup	Lecture on access to social rights for EU-citizens.	Presentation	Lecture by Otto Swedrup on the access to social rights for EUcitizens, based on results from the bEUcitizen-project.	University students; academic community
Sweden	Orebro Faculty of Law and Psychology.	Elena Ioriatti	Formulation of rights and European legal discourse: any theory behind?".	Presentation	Presentation by Elena Ioriatti and acknowledgment bEUcitizen.	Academic community
Sweden		Sara Stendahl; Otto Swedrup	Blog entry: "Where there is a will – there is a way"; a heated debate about access to education for children of migrating EU-citizens in Sweden.	http://beucitizen.eu/if-there-is-a-will-there-is-a-way-a-heated-debate-about-access-to-education-for-children-of-migrating-eu-citizens-in-sweden/		Academic community; general public
Switzerland		Monica Ferrin	Blog entry: The impact of the economic crisis on EU-nationals mobility: new challenges for EU citizenship?	http://beucitizen.eu/the-impact-of-the-economic-crisis-on-eu-nationals-mobility-new-challenges-for-eu-citizenship/		Academic community; general public
The Netherlands	Royal Dutch Academy of Arts and Sciences KNAW, Amsterdam.	Frans van Waarden	KNAW Seminar on 'Citizenship and Governance'.	Program	FvW Lecture on 'The Conditions for Participatory Governance'.	Academic Community
The Netherlands		Hanneke van Eijken	Recipient of a major literary award for Dr.van Eijken's poetry collection.	Press release	bEUcitizen mentioned in the press release.	General public; literary/academic community
The Netherlands	ACCESS Europe.		bEUcitizen's Open Call for Papers published in ACCESS Europe's February 2015 newsletter.	Newsletter ACCESS Europe 9 February		Academic community

				2015		
The Netherlands	KNAW; Utrecht University.	Maarten Prak	Conference: 3.0 Towards a New Understanding of the role of Citizens in our 21st Century Society.	http://beucitizen.eu/agenda/citizenship-3-0-towards-a-new-understanding-of-the-role-of-citizens-in-our-21st-century-society/		General public; academic community
The Netherlands	University College, Utrecht University.	Sybe de Vries; Frans van Waarden	Stimulus and Supervision of the Final Academic Theses of 3 Students of the International Liberal Arts and Sciences University College Utrecht.	http://www.uu.nl/en/research/project-for-upgrading-undergraduate-research/ur-thesis-groups/2015-2016/beucitizen-european-citizenship-research-project	The theses are the last major assignment before graduating. Topics written about in 2015 were: - a) Comparison of Minority Rights in Finland, Italy and Slovakia; b) a study of the Gender dimension of the mobility of young Greeks across Europe; and c) a study of the tension between maintaining EU's cultural diversity and EU's competition policy, focused on state aid for movies in the national language.	Academic Community; notably students and their families and friends
The Netherlands	Department of Public Administration, Utrecht University	Frans van Waarden	Guest lecture on 'Challenges of Europe: The Quest for Citizenship. Let me Challenge that -and you - a bit'.	Course Program		Academic Community; students
The Netherlands	Utrecht University and Europa Institute.	Sybe de Vries; Hanneke van Eijken	Presentation: bEUcitizen Project.	http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/PresentationsUtrechtFrame2015.pdf	Sybe de Vries and Hanneke van Eijken presented the bEUcitizen project at the FRAME project seminar.	Academic community
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Rosanne Oomkens	ESPANET conference. Odense, Denmark.	http://static.sdu.dk/mediafiles/D/E/E/%7BDEF435C5-0B73-47F9-9FED-991AC2828857%7DESPANet	Rosanne Oomkens presented a paper on migrant care work (research conducted on behalf of work package 9,	Academic community

				%20program.pdf	deliverable 9.6).	
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Hanneke van Eijken	Presentation on the Refugee Crisis, Kick-off meeting debatserie Europa en de Ander.	http://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cac he:fR77dI3yPLKJ:www.uu.nl/file/32661/download%3Fto ken%3DzDyp OEzM+&cd=1 &hl=nl&ct=cln k&gl=nl	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community; students
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Hanneke van Eijken	Presentation on EU citizenship and its constitutional context, Cultures, Citizenship and Human Rights book launch.	http://www.uu.nl/agenda/book-launch-cultures-citizenship-and-human-rights	Logo of bEUcitizen.	
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Hanneke van Eijken	Presentation on 'EU citizenship and Human Rights', FRAME WP 3: Underlying Conceptions of Human Rights, Democracy and Rule of Law.	http://sim.rebo.uu.nl/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/U-FRAME-workshop-program-22-January-2015.pdf	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Hanneke van Eijken	Presentation on the Advice of the CJEU on the accession to the ECHR, C-2/13	http://renforce.rebo.uu.nl/type-activiteiten/ro undtable-over-advies-europees-hof-van-justitie-over-toetreding-eu-tot-het-evrm/http://renforce.rebo.uu.nl/type-activiteiten/ro undtable-over-advies-europees-hof-van-justitie-over-toetreding-eu-tot-het-evrm/	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community
The Netherlands	Leiden University	Hanneke van Eijken	Presentation on EU citizenship and fundamental rights.	Invitation	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community

The Netherlands	Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Hanneke van Eijken	Key note speech, EU citizenship and the constitutionalisation of the European Union, at the Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs.	http://www.minbuza.nl/ecer/nieuws/2014/11/ecer-seminar-europees-burgerschap-en-constitutionalisering-van-de-eu.html	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Policymakers; politicians; academic community
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Hanneke van Eijken	Organization multidisciplinary debates on the refugee crisis 'Europa and the other.	http://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cache:fR77dI3yPLKJ:www.uu.nl/file/32661/download%3Ftoken%3DzDypOeZM+&cd=1&hl=nl&ct=clnk&gl=nl	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Hanneke van Eijken	Organization multidisciplinary debates on 'Terrorisme en de rechtsstaat' (Terrorism and the rule of law).	http://www.uu.nl/en/events/europe-and-the-other-multidisciplinary-reflections-on-the-refugee-crisis	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Hanneke van Eijken	Organization Roundtable Advice Court of Justice on the accession of the EU to the ECHR, Advice 2/13.	Program	Logo of bEUcitizen.	Academic community
		Hanneke van Eijken	European citizenship and the constitutionalisation of the European Union, Europa Law Publishing (2015).	http://www.europalawpublishing.com/NL/webshop/binnenkort-te-verschijnen/0/1/55171	BEUcitizen mentioned in a footnote.	General public; academic community; university students
		Hanneke van Eijken	De zaak Martens: studiefinanciering en het vrije verkeer van EU-burgers, SEW Tijdschrift voor Europees en Economisch Recht (2015), pp. 483-486.	http://dspace.library.uu.nl/handle/1874/322835	BEUcitizen mentioned in a footnote.	General public; academic community; university students
		Hanneke van Eijken	Het advies van het Hof van Justitie van de Europese Unie over de toetreding tot het EVRM, Het Nederlands Tijdschrift voor de	http://dspace.library.uu.nl/handle/1874/321248	BEUcitizen mentioned in a footnote.	General public; academic community;

			Mensenrechten (NTM/NJCM-Bulletin), jrg. 40 (2015), nr.2, pp. 203-211.			university students
		Hanneke van Eijken	H. van Eijken, De zaken S. en G. & O. en B.: Grenzeloze gezinnen en afgeleide verblijfsrechten, Nederlands Tijdschrift voor Europees recht (2014), pp. 319-324.	http://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cache:GLOsiThQn7UJ:dspace.library.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/1874/306737/verblijfsrechten.pdf%3Fsequence%3D1+&cd=1&hl=nl&ct=clnk&gl=nl	BEUcitizen mentioned in a footnote.	General public; academic community; university students
		Hanneke van Eijken	The European citizen as bearer of fundamental rights in a multi-layered legal order, in: Van den Brink, Luchtman & Scholten (eds.), Sovereignty in the shared legal order of the EU, Antwerpen: Intersentia (2015, pp. 249-298).	http://intersentia.be/nl/show/professionel/sovereignty-in-the-shared-legal-order-of-the-eu.html	BEUcitizen mentioned in a footnote.	General public; academic community; university students
		Alice Perenzin	Blog entry: Is unawareness the first barrier?	http://beucitizen.eu/is-unawareness-the-first-barrier/		Academic community; general public
The Netherlands		Hanneke van Eijken	Blog entry: Family life & European citizenship: The Strasbourg Court Decision in Jeunesse v. the Netherlands.	http://beucitizen.eu/family-life-european-citizenship-the-strasbourg-court-decision-in-jeunesse-v-the-netherlands/		Academic community; general public
The Netherlands		Susanne Heeger-Hertter	Blog entry: Residence in the home for the elderly – who has to pay the bill?	http://beucitizen.eu/residence-in-the-home-for-the-elderly-who-has-to-pay-the-bill/		Academic community; general public
The Netherlands		Mara Yerkes	Blog entry: Which rights, and for whom? Civil and social rights in Europe.	http://beucitizen.eu/which-rights-and-for-whom-civil-and-social-rights-in-europe/		Academic community; general public
United Kingdom	University of Oxford.	Martin Seeleib-Kaiser; Elaine Chase	Policy Essay.	http://social-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/12/RE3-Seeleib.pdf	Research essay on the topic of social rights of EU migrant citizens in cooperation with the Oxford Institute of Social	General public; academic community; interested university students

					Policy and the Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung London office. This research essay is a contribution to the ongoing debate about inner-EU migration and its policy consequences.	
United Kingdom	University of Oxford (with support from ESRC and Friedrich Ebert Stiftung).	Martin Seeleib-Kaiser; Frans Pennings	Conference "Making Free Movement Work".	Program		
United Kingdom	University of Oxford.	Martin Seeleib-Kaiser	Migrants, Citizens, Movers: Europe's Great Debate?	http://www.ox.ac.uk/event/migrants-citizens-movers-europe%E2%80%99s-great-debate	Presentation by Martin Seeleib-Kaiser.	General public; academic community
United Kingdom	Friedrich Ebert Foundation; Compas.	Martin Seeleib-Kaiser	EU-Immigration Fears: Who is to blame?	Presentation	Presentation by Martin Seeleib-Kaiser.	Politicians; policymakers; general public
United Kingdom		Martin Seeleib-Kaiser	Freedom of movement, EU Citizenship and the Need for a European Minimum Income Scheme.	http://www.migrantvoice.org/blog/freedom-of-movement-eu-citizenship-and-the-need-for-a-european-minimum-income-scheme.html	Acknowledgement bEUcitizen.	
United Kingdom	Durham University, Institute of Medieval and Early Modern Studies.	Christopher Kissane; Chris Minns; Maarten Prak	Session with papers from the project in conference 'Cities and Citizenship', July 13, 2015.	https://www.dur.ac.uk/imes/events/?eventno=20694	Papers presented by Christopher Kissane, Chris Minns, Maarten Prak.	Academic community
United Kingdom		Chris Minns	Blog entry: Citizenship and the city-state: lessons from history?	http://beucitizen.eu/citizenship-and-the-city-state-lessons-from-history/		Academic community; general public
United Kingdom		Christopher Kissane	Blog entry: Citizenship, Free Movement, & the Dano Judgement	http://beucitizen.eu/citizenship-free-movement-the-dano-judgement/		Academic community; general public

United Kingdom		Bridget Anderson	Blog entry: What to do about refugees – in 50 words.	http://beucitizen.eu/what-to-do-about-refugees-in-50-words/		Academic community; general public
United States	American Political Science Association.	Viktor Koska	Paper presentation "Croatian citizenship identity following the accession to EU" at the APSA annual meeting in San Francisco, 3-6 September 2015.	http://convention2.allacademic.com/one/apsa/apsa15/index.php?cmd=Online+Program+View+Person&selected_people_id=5714647&PHPSESSID=uu31299r15pl0bdja895a6h8c1		Academic community
Period 3						
Belgium	ECIT Foundation. Event hosted at the Maison des Associations Internationales	Sybe de Vries (UU)	Summer University on European Citizenship, 29/31-8-2016	http://beucitizen.eu/news/report-summer-university-on-european-citizenship/	The first introductory session consisted of presentations by Sybe de Vries on the barriers to the exercise of European rights and on the concept of European citizenship	academic community; university students
Belgium	European Commission	Sybe de Vries (UU)	Workshop on Cultures & Citizenship: Research & Innovation, 8-4-2016	https://ec.europa.eu/research/social-sciences/pdf/conferences/sc-workshop_04_2016_agenda.pdf	6/7-11-2015 European Commission, Belgium	Political stakeholders, policy makers
Belgium	COFACE	Yerkes, Mara A. (UU)	presentation at the COFACE-Families Europe conference 'Families on the Move' on 12 May	No evidence yet	upcoming	General public
Canada	University of Toronto	Dorota Lepianka (UU)	Hidden Populations: the Case of Domestic Workers in the Netherlands', at the Labour Law Research Network (LLRN) Conference, University of Toronto, Faculty of Law. June 25-27, 2017	Conference programme	upcoming	academic community; university students
Croatia	UNIZG	Vedrana Baričević	Contemporary security environment and security challenges for Croatia" (panel: Migration, borders, walls and new divides), presentation of results obtained within WP10.1. and 10.3 6/7-11-2015			Academic community
Croatia	UNIZG	Vedrana Baričević	Public Discussion: „Put u nepoznato“ (The Road to Nowhere) Vedrana Baričević participated on the discussion with a lecture „Izbjeglička i migracijska kretanja u Europi:		Student Club of Faculty of Political Sciences , Zagreb University	Academic community; general public

			temeljni pojmovi i statistički pokazatelji“ (Refugee and other migratory movements in Europe: key concepts and statistacal indicator). The lecture prepared for this panel presented the data collected within the working package 10. 9-11-2015			
Croatia	The Centre for the Study of Ethnicity, Citizenship and Migration (CEDIM)	Vedrana Baričević	Conference „Izazovi izbjegličke krize: granice, tranzit i integracija“ Challenges of refugee crisis: borders, tranzit and integration. Vedrana Baričević presented on data collected through bEUcitizen project. 30-11-2015			Academic community; general public
Croatia	UNIZG	Vedrana Baričević	Conference “Izazovi izbjegličke krize: granice, tranzit i integracija“ Challenges of refugee crisis: borders, tranzit and integration. Vedrana Baričević presented on data collected through bEUcitizen project. 19/21-12-2015			Academic community; general public
Croatia	Center for Peace Studies, Zagreb	Vedrana Baričević	Open discussion: How Closure of the Balkan Route Violates Human and Refugee Rights. Vedrana Baričević presented the findings from WP 10.1. and 10.3. relating to rights of migrants and refugees and discussed the implications of new immigration control mechanisms established in the Western Balkans and the EU. 20-6-2016			academic community; university students, genral public
Croatia	Department of Ethnology and Cultural Anthropology of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences (University of Zagreb) and the Institute for Migration and Ethnic Studies	Vedrana Baričević	Academic Conference „Contemporary Migration Trends and Flows on the Territory of Southeast Europe“. Vedrana Baričević presented the findings of the case study under bEUcitizen WP10.3. relating to economic integration of refugees in Croatia in the context of Europeanization of asylum policies. 10/11-11-2016			academic community; university students
Czech Republic	Masaryk University Brno	Wieger Bakker	Extra curricular intense course “The European dimension of local policymaking”at the annual elective (master) course on the European Dimension of Local Policy Making, Faculty of Social Studies (Nov. 2015, 28 Nov. – 1 Dec. 2016)	Programme of the course, ppt presentation	Annual in November (from 2012 until 2016) no specific day	academic community; university students
Czech Republic	Mazarikova Univerzita	HLOUŠEK, Vít (MUNI)	Regular seminars (twice a year in February and June) with the doctoral students of the Faculty of Social Studies in the fields of International Relations and European Studies that included presentations of the project and its ongoing outcomes. In the period you mentioned the exact dates of these seminars are 4			academic community; university students

			February 2016, 22 June 2016, and 1 February 2017			
Denmark	UCPH	Silvia Adamo	Presentation on bEUcitizen Research Project to Management Team of the Faculty of Law 12-11-2015	ppt presentation		academic community; university students
Denmark	UCPH	Silvia Adamo (UCPH)	Lecture: The State and Migration – A View from Law and Justice (MA Course: International Migration) 23-11-2015	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students
Denmark	Univeristy of Copenhagen, Centre for Advanced Migration Studies	Silvia Adamo (UCPH)	Lecture: Integration Law in Denmark and EU – Right to Integration, or Duty to Integrate? (MA Course: International Migration) 11-4-2016	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students
Denmark	Copenhagen - Den store mødesal	Cathrine Jacqueson (UCPH)	Presentation at the Ministry of Employment on access to welfare benefits for Union workers, Temadag: Fri bevægelighed i EU – adgang til velfærdsydelse for vandrende arbejdstagere, 26-9-2016			Policy makers
Germany	Goethe-University Frankfurt	Sandra Seubert (GUF)	International Workshop: Beyond renationalization and parlamentarization: what ways to overcome the EU's crisis of democratic representation? 23/24-6-2016	http://beucitizen.eu/agenda/international-workshop-beyond-renationalization-and-parlamentarization-what-ways-to-overcome-the-eus-crisis-of-democratic-representation/	Moderation of Panel II: Political conflict and democratic representation in the EU.	academic community; university students, general public
Germany	Goethe-University Frankfurt	Sandra Seubert (GUF)	International Workshop: Beyond renationalization and parlamentarization: what ways to overcome the EU's crisis of democratic representation? 23/24-6-2016	http://beucitizen.eu/agenda/international-workshop-beyond-renationalization-and-parlamentarization-what-ways-to-overcome-the-eus-crisis-of-democratic-representation/	Moderation of Panel III: The European Parliament in Eu's system of democratic representation.	academic community; university students, general public
Hungary	Central European University	Marie - Pierre Granger (CEU)	Conference: 'The application of the EU 'federal bill of rights' to states: European traits from a comparative perspective', organized by the Centre for Social Sciences, of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, the	https://ceur.ceu.edu/events/2016-06-21/application-eu-federal-bill-rights-	Marie-Pierre Granger, presentation of a paper on 'The 'domestic' drivers of federalisation	academic community; university students, general public

			CEU Department of Legal Studies and the CEU Center for European Union Research (CEUR), 21-6-2016	states-european-traits-comparative-perspective link to the event's poster: https://ceur.ceu.edu/sites/ceur.ceu.edu/files/attachme nt/event/225/federalbillofr ightsconferenc eprogramiune 212016_0.pdf	around rights: the EU case', M.-P. Granger (Central European University). (Paper publication in the European Journal of Law Reform).	
Hungary	Central European University	Marie - Pierre Granger (CEU), Sybe De Vries (UU), Henry de Waele (Antwerp University), Orsolya Salat (CEU), PROF. HENRI DE WAELE (University of Antwerp).	Roundtable: 'The EU and the protection of civil rights in Europe – what is the added value?', organized by the CEU Center for European Union Research (CEUR), and supported by EU FP7 funded within the bEUCitizen project. 8-2-2016	Link to the event: https://ceur.ceu.edu/event/s/2016-02-08/eu-and-protection-civil-rights-europe-what-added-value ; link to event's poster: https://ceur.ceu.edu/sites/ceur.ceu.edu/files/attachme nt/event/203/feb-8-wp-and-roundtable-postermpg.pdf		academic community; university students, general public
Hungary	Central European University Center for European Union Research	Robert Csehi and Uwe Puetter (CEU)	Public lecture entitled 'The role of national parliaments in EU decision-making and the euro crisis – the case of Finland'. Peter Saramo, the Counsel of the Grand Committee (EU affairs) of the Finnish parliament gave a talk about the euro crisis decision-making which unfolded at the national level and within the Finnish parliament and how they were linked to EU-level policy action, 31 March 2016	http://archive .ceu.hu/node/ 44496		academic community; university students, general public
Ireland	Maynooth University	Prof. Michael Doherty & Dr. Delia Ferri (MU)	Conference " The EU Social Market Economy:Challenges and Opportunities", 23-9-2016	https://ilg2.org/2016/09/10 /conference- the-eu-social- market- economy- challenges- and- opportunities		academic community; university students, general public

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Israel	Hebrew University of Jerusalem	Dana Halevy & John Gal (Oxford Univ)	Data presentation from the project at a recent colloquium on social rights, 11-1-2017			Academic community
Italy	University of Trento	Sybe de Vries (UU)	Participation to the Seminar 'Barriers' to the Exercise of EU Citizenship's Rights: Factual and Legal Analysis, 12-5-2016	http://webmagazine.unitn.it/evento/giurisprudenza/9196/barriers-to-the-exercise-of-eu-citizenship-rights-factual-and-legal		academic community; university students
Italy	University of Trento	Maria Teresa Solis Santos (phd, University of Antwerp)	Participation to the Seminar 'Barriers' to the Exercise of EU Citizenship's Rights: Factual and Legal Analysis, 12-5-2016 Presentation on the topic 'From Legal towards factual barriers to the exercise of the EU citizenship's rights'	http://webmagazine.unitn.it/evento/giurisprudenza/9196/barriers-to-the-exercise-of-eu-citizenship-rights-factual-and-legal		academic community; university students
Italy	Pisa University	A. Santero and G. Testore (UNITO)	«Nuove frontiere» nel discorso euroscettico della Lega Nord. Genere, omogenitorialità e Islam [translation: "New borders" in the Lega Nord's Euroscepticism. Gender, same sex parents and Islam]. Populism, new right-wing and new parties: what kind of political discourses in Europe? 10/11-6-2016	ppt presentation		academic community; university students, general public
Italy	University of Turin	Manuela Naldini, Joelle Long and Arianna Santero (UNITO)	bEUcitizen Seminar "Families in Italy and in Europe: what citizenship?" 20-10-2016	Description of the seminar		academic community; university students
Portugal	ISCSP -Lisboa	Dorota Lepianka (UU)	Stream 6: 'At the edge of the welfare state: Marginal populations as policy challenge' for ESPAnet Conference, 14/16 -9-2017	http://espanetlisbon2017.eu/streams/	upcoming	academic community; university students, general public, field experts
Romania	Research Institute for Quality of Life - Romanian Academy, Faculty of Sociology and Social Work - University of Bucharest	Bridget Anderson (Oxford Univ)	'How fragile is the world... migration and the politics of mobility' keynote mid-term conference Sociology of Migration Research Network of the European Sociological Association, 2-9-2016	Conference programme		academic community; university students, field experts
Romania	Bucharest Conference on Qualitative	Wieger Bakker (UU)	Presentation " European Citizenship and promoting a European Civic Culture", September 25 2015	Ppt presentation		academic community; university

	Research in Communication					students, field experts
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo	Sandra Seubert (GUF)	bEUcitizen conference, 29/6/2016 and 1/7/2016	http://beucitizen.eu/news/beucitizen-conference-in-oviedo/		academic community; university students
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo	Graham Finlay	'Concepts of Citizenship' at the bEU, 29-6-2016	Slides of the presentation		academic community; university students
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo	Wieger Bakker	Workshop "Future Scenarios European Citizenship 2030", 30-06-2016	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo	Dorota Lepianka (UU)	WP10 panel for bEU Citizens conference, 30-6-2016	Slides of the presentation		academic community; university students
Spain	XII Congreso Español de Sociología	Hans-Peter van den Broek (Univ Oviedo)	Presentation <i>Entre la espada y la pared: musulmanes liberales entre islamófobos e islamistas</i> , from 30-6 to 2-7-2016	Attendance and presentation Certificate		field experts and researchers
Spain	XII Congreso Español de Sociología	Hans-Peter van den Broek (Univ Oviedo)	Presentation <i>El enigma de la derecha radical populista: éxito europeo pero fracaso español</i> , from 30-6 to 2-7-2016	Attendance and presentation Certificate		field experts and researchers
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Wieger Bakker	Guest lecture on EU citizenship in an advanced elective bachelor course on European Governance for a multi-disciplinary group of students at Utrecht University (2015 and 2016)			academic community; university students
The Netherlands	The Netherlands Presidency of the Council of the European Union	Sybe de Vries (UU)	Seminar National Policy Application of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, 19-2-2016	http://english.eu2016.nl/events/2016/02/19/policy-application-of-the-eu-charter-of-fundamental-rights		Policy makers
The Netherlands	Utrecht University, School of Governance	Wieger Bakker	Citizenship workshop for the master program on Public administration and policy making, Utrecht School of Governance, 12-01-2016 and 12-04-2017	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students
The Netherlands	Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Sybe de Vries (UU)	Seminar New Privacy Protection in the EU, 11-4-2016	http://www.minbuza.nl/ecer/agenda/2016/maart/nieuwe-privacybescherming-in-de-eu.html		Policy makers
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Wieger Bakker	Scenario workshop Utrecht team, 19-05-2016	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students

The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Wieger Bakker	Scenario workshop for invited scholars and students, 10-3-2017	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Patrick Wallis (LSE)	Workshop: Apprenticeship in early modern Europe, 3-7-2016	Programme of the workshop		academic community; university students
The Netherlands	Maastricht	Wieger Bakker	2 workshops (around 75 participants in total) on EU citizenship and education. The focus was on the fit between civic education, the EU and the new generation. Title: 'Exploring the Value of Education for the EU and for EU Citizenship', 8-2-2017	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students
The Netherlands	Maastricht	Wieger Bakker	Presentation at a large Model European Union youth conference with over 200 participants from 26 member states in Maastricht on the occasion of 25 year Treaty of Maastricht, 7/9-04-2017			academic community; university students
The Netherlands	Utrecht University	Maarten Prak (UU)	Access to the trade: monopoly and mobility in European craft guilds, 17th-18th centuries, 2-3-2017	Ppt presentation		academic community; university students
UK	Oxford University	Maarten Prak (UU)	Workshop URBAN GOVERNANCE AND THE FUTURE OF EUROPEAN CITIZENSHIP, 16-1-2017	Programme of the workshop		academic community; university students
UK	Kings College London	Sarah Walker	Begging and the free movement of poverty. Talk for the Roma Discussion group seminar 'THE ROMA IN THE NEXUS OF HOMELESSNESS, BEGGING AND RACIALIZATION', 6-5-2016	Slides of the presentation		academic community; university students
UK	Worcester College, University of Oxford (UK).	Maarten Prak (UU)	Workshop: Urban governance and the future of European Citizenship, 17/18-02-2016 or 24/25-02-2016	Programme		academic community; university students
United States	Council for European Studies annual conference, Theme: Resilient Europe? Philadelphia, Double Tree by Hilton.	Orsolya Salát (CEU)	Organizer and chair of the panel entitled 'Integrating the Illiberal: European Hungary or Hungarian Europe'; paper presentation 'How European Legal Mechanisms Contribute to a Lowering of Protection of Rights and the Rule of Law', 16-4-2016	https://ces.cnfex.com/ces/2016/webprogram/Session5807.html ; https://ces.cnfex.com/ces/2016/webprogram/Paper14302.html		academic community; university students
United States	New School, New York	Bridget Anderson (Oxford University)	'Animals, Natives and Migration at the borders of Europe' The Invasive Other, Center for Public Scholarship, 21-4-2016	https://youtube.be/BS3Aybw09iU		academic community; university students
United States	UC Santa Cruz	Bridget Anderson (Oxford University)	'The Good, The Bad and The Ugly: citizenship and the politics of exclusion' opening keynote UC Santa Cruz Andrew W. Mellon Foundation John E. Sawyer Seminar series on non-citizenship, 6-10-2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qcnRhZ71mw		academic community; university students

		Ulla Neergaard (UCPH)	<i>A Scandinavian 'Rock' in EU Legal Scholarship – and Some Thoughts about Social Rights</i> , Europarättslig Tidsskrift ("Ulf Bernitz 80"), Sweden, 2015, pp. 113-123	http://jura.ku.dk/english/staff/research/?pure=en%2Fpublications%2Fa-scandinavian-rock-in-eu-legal-scholarship--and-some-thoughts-about-social-rights(7110d466-02de-4abe-a4c0-169a80e6631a)%2Fexport.html		General public; academic community; university students
		HLOUŠEK, Vít (MUNI)	<i>From region to nation and back again: Moravian parties' rhetoric and politics in the course of time. The Annual of Language & Politics and Politics of Identity</i> , Praha: Institute of Political Studies Faculty of Social Sciences Charles University, 2015, IX, pp. 5-22.	ISSN 1803-1757. (to be found at http://alppi.vedeckecasopisy.cz/publicFiles/00934.pdf)		General public; academic community; university students
		Schmidt-Kessel, Martin; Strünck, Christoph; Kramme, Malte (Hg.)	Im Namen der Verbraucher? Kollektive Rechtsdurchsetzung in Europa. [Jena]: JWV, Jenaer Wiss. Verl.-Ges (Schriften zu Verbraucherrecht und Verbraucherwissenschaften, Bd. 5). 2015	http://jwv.societas-shop.eu/index.php/shop/schriften-zu-verbraucherrecht-und-verbraucherwissenschaften/im-namen-der-verbraucher-kollektive-rechtsdurchsetzung-in-europa-detail.html		General public; academic community; university students
		HLOUŠEK, Vít.	From region to nation and back again: Moravian parties' rhetoric and politics in the course of time. The Annual of Language & Politics and Politics of Identity, Praha: Institute of Political Studies Faculty of Social Sciences Charles University, 2015, IX, pp. 5-22. ISSN 1803-1757. (Paper)	(to be found at http://alppi.vedeckecasopisy.cz/publicFiles/00934.pdf)		General public; academic community; university students
		Silvia Adamo (UCPH)	<i>Le système danois de protection sociale: équilibrer solidarité en Europe et immigration en temps de crise</i> Revue Française des Affaires Sociales no. 3/2015, Vol. n° 3, Nr. 2015/3, 2015, La Documentation Française	https://www.cairn.info/revue-francaise-des-affaires-sociales-2015-3-page-159.htm		General public; academic community; university students

		Ulla Neergaard (UCPH)	<i>Europe and the Welfare State – Friends, Foes, or..?</i> Yearbook of European Law, UK, 2016 (approximately 30 pages) Forthcoming	https://academic.oup.com/yel/article/35/1/341/2525283/Europe-and-the-Welfare-State-Friends-Foes-or		General public; academic community; university students
		Ulla Neergaard (UCPH)	'When Poverty Comes in at the Door, Love Flies Out the Window': The Influence of Eurozone Reforms Upon the Social Dimension of the EU – and Vice Versa', European Labour Law Journal, Belgium, 2016, pp. 168-204	https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2849599		General public; academic community; university students
		Ulla Neergaard (UCPH)	<i>Chartrets sociale rettigheders væsen</i> In Eva Ersbøll (ed.): EU's Charter om grundlæggende rettigheder DJØF Publishing, Denmark, 2016 (approximately 15 pages submitted), Forthcoming	http://www.orskningsdata.basen.dk/catalog/2346313111		General public; academic community; university students
		Cathrine Jacqueson (UCPH)	<i>From negligence to resistance: Danish welfare in the light of EU free movement law</i> <i>EU citizenship, free movement and residence-based Social Security Schemes</i> , Special issue ed. by Thomas Erhag, European Social Security, Vol 18(2), June 2016, pp.183-206	http://www.ejss.eu/pdf_file/ITS/EJSS_18_02_0183.pdf		General public; academic community; university students
		Cathrine Jacqueson (UCPH)	<i>Back to business – The Court in Alimanovic</i> Blog: BEUCitizen, 7 July 2016 < beucitizen.eu/back-to-business-the-court-in-alimanovic/ >	< beucitizen.eu/back-to-business-the-court-in-alimanovic/ >		General public; academic community; university students
		Silvia Adamo (UCPH)	<i>Protecting International Civil Rights in a National Context: Danish Law and Its Discontents</i> , Nordic Journal of International Law 85 (2016) 119–145	https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2773583		General public; academic community; university students
		Silvia Adamo (UCPH)	<i>Keeping up with the (Turkish) family: integration requirements for family reunification in Genc</i> Blog: EU Law Analysis, United Kingdom, 26 April 2016.	< eulawanalysis.blogspot.dk/2016/04/keeping-up-with-turkish-family.html >		General public; academic community; university students
		Yerkes, M.A., G. Dotti Sani and C. Solera.	Attitudes towards parenthood, partnership and social rights for diverse families: Evidence from a pilot study in five countries." Journal of Homosexuality.	Forthcoming. Accepted for publication 6 November 2016.		General public; academic community; university students
		Petr Kaniok	"National Parliaments and European Integration: A Collective Actor in the EU Political System ", Masaryk University Press	see https://is.muni.cz/obchod/baleni/100329	Article	General public; academic community; university students

		Isabel Shutes (Oxford)	(2016) 'Work-related Conditionality and the Access to Social Benefits of National Citizens, EU and Non-EU Citizens' - Accepted for Journal of Social Policy February 2016.	https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-social-policy/article/work-related-conditionality-and-the-access-to-social-benefits-of-national-citizens-eu-and-non-eu-citizens/B14099E22D389587FE1F0196DC1E978D	Journal article	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	(under review) 'Towards a New Politics of Migration' Ethnic and Racial Studies		Journal article	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson B.	(2016 Accepted)'The Politics of Pests: Immigration and the Invasive Other' Social Research		Journal article	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	(2015)'Migrant Domestic Workers: collisions and connections' Social Politics 22(4): 636-652		Journal article	General public; academic community; university students
		Finlay, G. and Mancini, J.M.	Finlay, G. and Mancini, J.M. (2015) "Her Life Within the Home': The Construction of Gender and Female Migrant Workers in the Republic of Ireland", forthcoming in Zahra Mehgani ed., Migrant Women Workers: Ethical and Political Issues, Routledge, 2015		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. & Hughes, V. (eds.) (2016) Citizenship and Its Others London: Palgrave		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. (In Press) "' Let language not betray us": Twisting the Lessons of Slavery' in Slavery Old and New: the meanings of freedom eds. L. Brace and O'Connell Davidson, J., London: Proceedings of the British Academy		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students

		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. (In Press) 'The Unworthy Citizen: a brief commentary' with M. Gibney in <i>Within and Beyond Citizenship</i> eds N. Sigona and R. Gonzalez, Stanford: Stanford University Press		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. (2016) Foreword <i>Migration, Squatting and Radical Autonomy</i> eds. P. Mudu and S. Chattopadhyay		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. (2015) 'Us and Them?' in <i>Migration as a Sign of the Times</i> eds. J.Gruber and Rettenbacher, S., Boston: Brill Rodopi		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. (2015) 'How Are We to Conceive of the Borders of the Future Citizen?' in <i>The Future Citizen Guide</i> , London: Tate		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. (2016) 'Against Fantasy Citizenship: the politics of migration and austerity' <i>Renewal</i> 24(1)		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Anderson, B.	Anderson, B. (2015) 'Critical Dialogue with Joseph Carens' <i>Perspectives on Politics</i> 13(3) American Political Science Association		book or book chapter	General public; academic community; university students
		Hans-Peter van den Broek y Tania Suárez Fernández	<i>Islamófobos contra islamistas, historia de un antagonismo simbiótico</i> , Claves 250, p.12.21 (2017)	pdf	article	General public; academic community; university students
		Martin Seeleib-Kaiser (UOXF)	Publication - Hard Evidence: how integrated are young EU migrants into the UK workforce?	https://theconversation.com/hard-evidence-how-integrated-are-young-eu-migrants-into-the-uk-workforce-56714	Online article	General public; academic community; university students

